

D5.2 Low-Level Design

The architecture of the DIRECTED Data Fabric

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Executive Summary

This deliverable builds upon the high-level architecture of the Data Fabric which was laid out in D5.1. This document, D5.2, describes the low-level architecture of the Data Fabric and describes the technical details. It is written in conjunction with D5.3, where data protection and ethical aspects of the Data Fabric are documented, and D5.4, where the implementation plan and forthcoming documentation are rolled out. Therefore, several cross-references will be found among D5.1, D5.2, D5.3 and D5.4 all together documenting the preparations necessary to successfully develop, deploy and operate the Data Fabric in DIRECTED.

The described architecture of the Data Fabric will serve as a reference architecture. It starts from top to bottom, with two main components ([Figure 11](#)), the authorization part alongside the Spatial Data Infrastructure (SDI). Separating both follows the modular design of the Data Fabric, ensuring a high degree of re-usability. Both parts are built upon proven Open Source Solutions in their respective fields and are informed by the needs of the stakeholders in the Real World Labs (RWL).

The SDI covers the entire process from data registration and integration, storage and maintenance up to discovery and access. An orchestration service is introduced that can be used to continuously ingest and update data, as well as allows users to define and execute model chains. All application programming interfaces (APIs) are based on open standards and enable an easy integration with data sources and models outside the DIRECTED project.

The authorization part provides means to facilitate data protection, and secure and legit access to internal and external data sources. Here, the Data Steward adding and managing data and model chains has a central role to define and to manage access. The defined policies are also enforced in a machine-readable way, such that model chains of users can only access the respective data sources. The metadata is enriched to facilitate and track GDPR compliance,

In order to address auditability and to allow scrutiny of results of the Data Fabric, the model runs and incorporated data is tracked and stored as metadata. This allows to re-produce the model execution and to further validate and audit model outputs.

The architecture design presented in this deliverable is focussed on the thematic user stories and technical requirements of the RWLs in DIRECTED. All RWL use-cases have been further detailed and expanded compared to Deliverable D5.1. The selected user stories per RWL address key challenges of interoperability identified within DIRECTED and will therefore directly contribute to an improved interoperability and the project's goals in improving DRR and CCA measures.

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List of Abbreviations

ACRONYM	DEFINITION
AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure
API	Application Programming Interface
AuthN	Authentication
AuthZ	Authorization
CCA	Climate Change Adaptation
CDS	(Copernicus) Climate Data Store
COG	Cloud optimised GeoTIFF
CRUD	Create Read Update Delete
DMP	Data Management Plan
DRM	Disaster Risk Management
DRR	Disaster Risk Reduction
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GeoTIFF	Spatial Tagged Image File Format
GIS	Geographic Information System
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HTML	Hypertext Markup Language

JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
k8s	Kubernetes
LMF	Loss Modelling Framework
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OTC	Open Telekom Cloud
RWL	Real World Lab
SDI	Spatial Data Infrastructure
STAC	Spatio Temporal Asset Catalog
WP	Work Package
WFS	Web Feature Service
WMS	Web Map Service
ZARR	community project to develop specifications and software for storage of large N-dimensional typed arrays: https://zarr.dev

1 Introduction

The Data Fabric will showcase how an improved technical interoperability supports better CCA and DRM in the RWLs. The concept of a Data Fabric is outlined in [Figure 1](#) and shows different layers of the system. The horizontal layers depict the technical layers. The vertical layers connect the technical ones based on particular use case requirements. Each RWL brings its own use cases, which may have similar requirements but different foci or priorities. Therefore, the technical architecture has to be able to handle the following challenges:

- Different RWL will have different requirements on the data infrastructure
- For all RWL, not all components/orchestrations have the same importance

The main goal of the architectural design is to define architectural template descriptions which are designed to be composable for tailored use cases. The low-level architecture builds upon the high-level architecture design described by D5.1 and the requirements of the RWLs highlighted therein.

In the following, the Data Fabric layers are explained shortly in a less technical wording. Each layer will reference relevant subsections of Section 2 to give a deeper insight of the particular implementation. In Section 3 the implementations are explained in the context of the selected RWL use cases.

Figure 1: High-Level concept view of the Layers of the DIRECTED Data Fabric.

Users: Access restriction to particular data is a cross-cutting concern. While single services may implement specific authorization rules, the overall approach focuses on a single instance that enforces rules to protect access to the Data Fabric and data flowing out of the Data Fabric. User or service based access can also be generated by an external identity provider such as an existing user data base at the RWL, or other third parties (see [Section 2.7: Data Authorization and Stewardship](#)).

Graphical User Interface: The Graphical User Interfaces (GUI) provides access to the interoperable components and information products. The Data Fabric provides dedicated web applications as well as the integration into existing tools and GIS applications (e.g., [QGIS](#)) of the RWLs (see [Section 2.3: Data Integration and Ingestion](#) and [Section 2.8: Applications](#)).

Model & Data Catalog: Makes metadata about data and process models via standardised metadata descriptions available, and allows discovering data and services provided through the Data Fabric via federated catalogue search. (see [Section 2.1: SDI Gateway](#), [Section 2.4: Data Publication](#) and [Section 2.5: Data Discovery](#))

Models: Facilitates simplified access and chaining of models by exposing well-known and necessary process models via interoperable machine-readable interfaces such as e.g. OGC APIs (see [Section 2.2: Model Interoperability and Process Orchestration](#)).

Data: Connects to different kinds of local data formats, e.g., file based, RWL specific databases (see [Section 2.3: Data Integration and Ingestion](#)).

External Services: Integrate existing data services via API by implementing adapters for needed data sources to leverage fleXible data access and data processing via interoperable Web interfaces.

2 Overview of SDI Technical Components in the Data Fabric

This section describes the technical components of the Spatial Data Infrastructure as part of the DIRECTED Data Fabric.

2.1 SDI Gateway

To reach the goals of the DIRECTED project, a core requirement is the interoperability of data, models, communication and governance. Interoperability can be facilitated by using open standards (see D2.1). Thus, the Data Fabric will make use of open standards wherever beneficial. A central component to support this is a gateway for the **spatial data infrastructure (SDI)** based on the OGC API suite of standards (see Deliverable D2.1). With these standards, users will be able to discover, access and process data in an interoperable and clearly defined way. Moreover, integration with other software systems and tools will be facilitated, as many mainstream software components in the geo domain already implement OGC APIs or OGC Web Services.

The gateway serves as a single entry point for the Data Fabric. It forwards requests to internal components which are responsible for processing these and creating a response. An important task of the gateway apart from providing a uniform view on the Data Fabric is the enforcement of defined policies to external traffic via authentication and authorisation components (see [Section 2.7](#)). Having a single entry point with access control allows flexibility with the deployment of underlying components which handle the main load when processing user requests. Some advantages are a better scaling, the option to have small instances which are easier to manage, a lightweight handling of traffic and fewer downtimes.

Although the OGC APIs are relatively new (the first OGC API standard was officially approved in 2019) there are already mature implementations. One of them is pygeoapi which is an open source server implementation written in Python and capable of deploying RESTful OGC API endpoints using [OpenAPI](#), JSON, and HTML (<https://pygeoapi.io/>). Pygeoapi supports most of the OGC API standards, for some of them being a reference implementation. Reference implementations are officially certified by the OGC after passing a set of predefined tests. [Table 1](#) gives an overview of the implementation status of different OGC APIs by pygeoapi.

Table 1: Overview of the standards implemented by pygeoapi (source: <https://docs.pygeoapi.io/en/stable/introduction.html#standards-support>).

Standard	Support
OGC API - Features	Reference Implementation
OGC API - Coverages	Implementing
OGC API - Maps	Implementing
OGC API - Tiles	Reference Implementation
OGC API - Processes	Compliant
OGC API - Records	Implementing
OGC API - Environmental Data Retrieval	Reference Implementation
SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog	Implementing

[Figure 2](#) shows the main components of pygeoapi. At its centre is the core API, which provides the functionality to interact with spatial data. It has to be configured by the administrator for the specific deployment, including the registration of datasets and processes. An Open API document is generated automatically by the OpenAPI component. On top of the core API sits a web framework, which is responsible for serving the application over the web. With Flask, Starlette and Django different options are available. An important aspect of pygeoapi's architecture is the flexible plugin mechanism. A number of built-in data provider plugins exist which support storage and publishing of a wide range of data types and formats served from different backends as databases, file systems and services. New provider plugins can be integrated if necessary. Before users can access data via pygeoapi the data have to be ingested into a suitable storage within the Data Fabric (see [Section 2.3](#) and [2.4](#)). Alternatively, pygeoapi can integrate data in a federated way by serving as a proxy for external data sources without storing a copy of the data (see [Section 2.3](#)). For example, it offers built-in providers for forwarding requests from/to a Web Map Service (WMS) or Web Feature Service (WFS), or even Sensor Things API (STA). Data from external providers which support only specific, potentially non-standardized access mechanisms could be imported using dedicated processes via the OGC API Processes standard or proxied through other suitable OGC APIs. Processes will also be used for executing the models

provided by the different project partners (see [Section 2.2](#)). The Oasis Loss Modelling Framework (LMF) will also be wrapped into the OGC patterns, in order to benefit from existing resources in the insurance sector.

By providing a streamlined, standards-based framework for the models and data, users themselves do not have to interact with a multitude of services within the Data Fabric. Specific user interfaces and applications will further lower the barrier of model and data access (see [Section 2.8](#)) and enable users to find solutions for their problems at hand (see [Chapter 3](#)). This ensures that the user experience is not cumbersome and difficult to understand, which could be a serious barrier to dissemination; not only to the RWLs, but also to the wider communities the RWLs are part of. Thus, using pygeoapi as a proxy within the DIRECTED project offers standardisation through its backing in OGC, and provides a simplified framework for accessing model outputs for specific user requirements and data for model needs.

Figure 2: Component diagram of pygeoapi (source: <https://docs.pygeoapi.io/en/stable/how-pygeoapi-works.html>).

2.2 Model Interoperability and Process Orchestration

As described in Deliverable D5.1 the models brought into the DIRECTED project by different partners of the consortium play a central role in achieving the goals of Disaster Risk Management and Climate Change Adaptation. In this section, we describe the technical aspects of achieving model interoperability and explain the relevant components of the Data Fabric.

When discussing model interoperability on a technical level, mainly two aspects have to be considered:

1. Data and metadata standards (formats/encodings)
2. Interface standards

When using data and metadata standards (see Deliverable D2.1 for a detailed list of options) it is ensured that outputs of a model can be easily used in other software components. Moreover, different data sources, e.g. from data providers or outputs from other models, can be used as input without major efforts in understanding the data and transforming or preprocessing them. Using metadata standards helps understanding and finding data.

At this stage, models still have to be executed manually by someone who understands the tool to a sufficient degree. Moreover, a suitable runtime environment and the necessary hardware has to be available. This makes executing models and especially chaining different models cumbersome and time-consuming. Thus, apart from using data and metadata standards, it is recommended to use interface standards in addition. Candidates for interface standards (OWS, OGC APIs) have previously been described in Deliverable D2.1.

[Figure 3](#) provides an overview of the planned architecture to support model interoperability based on the OGC API Processes standard. A central component is pygeoapi (see [Section 2.1](#)) which implements - among others - the OGC API Processes standard. Users (and applications) can make HTTP requests to pygeoapi via the standardised API to run models, check the status of the execution and get the results. Pygeoapi parses the requests and delegates them to a process orchestrator, which is responsible for actually executing the processes, considering the specific software and hardware needs. In order to facilitate the orchestration, the models should be wrapped into containerized applications, e.g. via Docker or Kubernetes (k8s).

For the process orchestrator component, several options are available:

- Workflow orchestration frameworks, e.g.
 - prefect (<https://www.prefect.io/>)
 - Argo Workflows (<https://argoproj.github.io/workflows/>)
 - Apache Airflow (<https://airflow.apache.org/>)
- Custom (Python) applications using Kubernetes
 - k8s jobs are created via the k8s API which will execute one of the containerized applications. Communication of inputs/outputs is handled via cloud object storage.
 - pygeoapi deployments are created via the k8s API and subsequently processes are started via OGC API Processes requests. Communication of inputs/outputs is handled via OGC API Processes.

The favoured solution is to use the prefect framework. It provides out-of-the-box features like monitoring, logging, scheduling and a UI. Apart from this, there is already a prefect job manager [implementation for pygeoapi](#).

Data ingestion might make use of the same processing infrastructure as well (see [Section 2.3](#) for details).

Figure 3: Overview of the architecture supporting model interoperability based on the OGC API Processes standard. The process orchestrator picks the right model based on the request and facilitates its execution, ensuring the availability of the desired hardware.

2.3 Data Integration and Ingestion

Within the Data Fabric, data ingestion and data integration are two different approaches to providing data. Data integration focuses on the integration of external data, which is made discoverable and accessible in the same way as data that is directly available within the Data Fabric. Data ingestion can be seen both as manual work to upload data into the system and as an automated process for continuous data insertion. Manual data ingestion is mainly conducted by a Data Steward or data administrator by first making the data available in the system and to add metadata about that data.

Certain tools and interfaces are provisioned by the Data Fabric to leverage data integration and ingestion. They are used in intermediary components to seamlessly integrate from various external sources (see [Figure 5](#)). Internally, the same tools can also be used to realise data ingestion.

In general, it is advisable to use interoperable service interfaces to make data available, even if individual, non-standardised workflows may remain possible, but stay the exception and are kept internal. The manual provisioning of data is depicted in [Figure 6](#) involving a Data Steward who publishes local data by uploading it, describing its metadata and registering it at a data discovery service.

Automated data ingestion is outlined in [Figure 4](#) and describes an automated process which has to consider three key steps:

1. External data access: The system connects to and retrieves data from various sources. Access to external data can either be direct or by re-using existing adapter tools provided by the Data Fabric.
2. Data processing: Ingested data undergoes processing, which may include conversion, transformation, merging, and updating of local data and caches.
3. Metadata resolution: The ingestion process automatically extracts metadata from the ingested data. The process shall create and update catalogue records to maintain an up-to-date data inventory.

Concrete architecture and implementation of the pipeline is dependent on things:

- Data source and data format
- Necessary (pre-)processing
- Targeted data storage and format

Therefore, the actual ingestion pipeline can only be described in general here, but can be discussed in more detail on a use case (see [Section 3](#)).

An automated data ingestion process can be initiated through multiple mechanisms:

- External API: The process can be triggered via an external API call, providing flexibility for integration with other systems.
- Scheduled Jobs: Internal processes may be triggered by external schedulers, such as local Cron jobs or Kubernetes jobs in cloud environments.

Both approaches can be combined to re-use existing strategies and the given execution environment to trigger and run processes. By wrapping the ingestion process as an OGC process, it can become executable from external systems via process orchestrator ([Section 2.2](#)). This would allow the system to “eat its own dogfood” by utilising its own standardised interfaces. Data sources to be used in DIRECTED have been listed in Deliverables D5.1 and D2.1. Selected examples will follow in the subsequent sections.

Figure 4: Continuous process of data ingestion. The lower box wraps the process to import external data sources. The pipeline can be triggered manually or automatically (e.g., based on a regular timing). During the integration, the metadata is generated/updated and the data is registered in the data catalogue and made available.

Figure 5: Access of external data via adapter tools. Different dedicated adaptors link to corresponding formats and interfaces for data access.

2.4 Data Publication

As discussed in [Section 2.3](#), data can be ingested and integrated into the Data Fabric using different mechanisms. As a result of data ingestion, the data reside in data storages which can be very heterogeneous and depend - amongst others - on data types, formats, size, intended use and security level. This includes Cloud Object Storage (e.g. Amazon S3) which are regularly used for cloud-optimised raster formats like Cloud Optimized GeoTIFF (COG) or Zarr, databases, files in traditional file systems or services encapsulating and providing data like Elasticsearch instances. At this point, data is only accessible within the system itself. Before external users or applications can use the data, they have to be published in a clear process which includes not only technical but also organisational aspects like access permissions and licences. [Figure 6](#) shows such a process including key actors and components. A Data Steward publishes data to a store within the Data Fabric. Metadata is derived either automatically or manually by the Data Steward. It might also be possible to derive parts of the metadata automatically, while other parts need a manual review. In either case the Data Steward tests and verifies the metadata which is then stored in a dedicated metadata store, optimally in a standardised format like ISO 19139. Part of this qualified data and metadata publication is the formulation of access permissions and data licences to be compliant with GDPR or other legal requirements. In case data should be published which indicate a high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons, a data protection impact assessment (DPIA) has to be part of this process (see D5.3). Once data is stored, the service responsible for publishing the data is configured with the SDI gateway, and metadata is prepared and validated, the actual publication can be concluded.

Users can now either access data directly (in case data location is known to the user beforehand) or the data appears in the result list of some query in a data catalogue where the metadata has been published. Access to data and metadata is possible using standardised APIs (see [Section 2.1](#)). It does not matter whether the data is made available via upload, integrated via a data adapter or only contains links to external sources. Depending on the type of data different interoperable APIs might be used:

- Vector data (points, lines, polygons):
 - OGC API Features, OGC API Environmental Data Retrieval
- Raster data
 - OGC API Coverages, OGC API Environmental Data Retrieval
- Sensor time-series data
 - OGC Connected System API
- Maps
 - OGC API Maps, OGC API Tiles
- Metadata
 - OGC API Records, STAC

Figure 6: Data publication and access. Data can be found through a dedicated interface (proxied through a web front end). The access of the data (here as an example for type feature) is handled separately. The Data Steward adds and manages data in the Data Fabric.

2.5 Data Discovery

Data from the Data Fabric can only be fully used, if it can be easily discovered and integrated. Various types of resources are available within the Data Fabric:

- Data with thematic, spatial and temporal dimensions
- Services that enable access to data and processes
- Process and model descriptions

In addition, users can run processes that generate new data based on selected processes and some input data. This output data should also be discoverable, so appropriate metadata descriptions need to be attached to it, just as part of the overall process. A user may not be aware of all resources, so a discovery service is the first address to find out what the Data Fabric has to offer.

The OGC API Web standard family provides different metadata services which allow discovery. Currently, the OGC API for Records is a draft but builds upon common OGC API patterns to provide metadata records under a collection. We will establish a hybrid approach in the Data Fabric that combines the OGC API Records for dynamically updated data resources and the Spatio Temporal Asset Catalog (STAC) for external data, as e.g. the Copernicus Climate Data Store (CDS). The search interface for the user will hide this complexity and no prior knowledge of how or where to find the specific data source will be required.

In order to support the user by data discovery, the data integration pipelines can update the metadata and calculate facets and statistics that help to describe and to identify data resources (see [Figure 7](#)).

Figure 7: Overview of the interplay between ingestion pipelines and discovery of data sets. Metadata is created or updated during the integration process. The calculation of facets and statistics support the discovery process.

2.6 Taxonomy

The connection between data, models, and metadata is a crucial aspect in keeping consistency with the work in the Data Fabric, as well as the findability, and reusability, of the project's resources. Thus, data within the consortium has been closely documented and monitored in accordance with a metadata naming structure to support the Connectivity Hub (developed by SEI), an open source taxonomy. More details on the Connectivity Hub can be found in D2.1.

Brief summary of approach

The Climate Connectivity Hub is a “search and discovery” tool that helps users find relevant knowledge (e.g. shared challenges, solutions, lessons learned etc) and organizations working on Climate Change Adaptation (CCA) and Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) issues. The Connectivity Hub is driven by a taxonomy that is being developed in response to user needs. The IPCC glossary and UNDRR taxonomy, considered the most robust sources of definitions in the fields of CCA and DRR respectively, serve as seed taxonomies. This base taxonomy is further developed in the following ways ([Figure 9](#)):

a.) Taxonomies (i.e. sets of keywords) belonging to platforms already featured on the previous version of the Connectivity Hub, such as weADAPT and Climate-ADAPT, are imported for manual mapping to the newly created taxonomy (IPCC and UNDRR). Where terms do not match the taxonomy, keywords from the platform data become ‘candidate’ terms for the taxonomy and are then subject to expert review in DIRECTED.

b.) A Large Language Model is applied across content (platform content describing climate change projects) that either initially lacked keywords or had keywords that were unaligned with the taxonomy scope. This provides additional ‘candidate’ keywords which need expert review or consultation before they can be accepted or rejected from the taxonomy.

The more specific taxonomy in DIRECTED will be tailored by:

a.) New taxonomies relevant to DIRECTED (e.g. on flood resilience, governance, co-production, modelling) and the RWLs incorporated to address gaps in the ‘seed’ taxonomies. These include the Myriad-EU glossary and the Society for Risk Analysis Glossary.

b.) Terms and concepts which have significance to the Data Fabric and its objectives manually curated from the Directed tool descriptions and user storylines being developed with RWLs.

Figure 8: Taxonomy mapping process.

Figure 9: High-level overview of wider taxonomy development process.

This knowledge map is visualized through a set of nodes on the front-end of the Climate Connectivity Hub (Figure 8). The Connectivity Hub already visualizes data from a number of sources:

- [The Resilience Platform](#), an online space to capture, access, co-create and advance the latest resilience knowledge;
- [Climate-ADAPT](#), the European Climate Adaptation Platform;
- [PreventionWeb](#), the knowledge-sharing program of the United Nations International Strategy for Disaster REduction (UNISDR);
- [Eldis](#), a knowledge-sharing platform on development issues, and BRIDGE, a specialized gender and development research and information service, both hosted by the Institute of Development Studies at the University of Sussex; and

- [weADAPT](#), the global climate adaptation platform and network of the Stockholm Environment Institute.
- [CORDIS](#), EU Research and Development projects.

Figure 10: Visualization of data in the Connectivity Hub.

Taxonomy development process

In DIRECTED, new additions to the taxonomy, such as definitions and synonyms (where relevant to flood risk modelling, governance or co-production, for example) will be verified with RWL stakeholders and experts to verify and validate the taxonomy. Experts can also provide ‘scope notes’ describing the variety of ways in which terms may be interpreted and thus applied in different decision domains.

This will be of value to the Data Fabric as it will provide a contextual glossary of terms that the user can easily view, for example when hovering the cursor over a word that could be interpreted differently, either by different disciplines or by different stakeholders. We anticipate that this will create a shared understanding of concepts, assumptions and model outputs in the Data Fabric, as well as improve communication between stakeholder groups. As such, this will also link to D4.3 on the data distillation framework which will explore assumptions in model and data use.

Use and benefits in the Data Fabric

The Data Fabric will connect to the Connectivity Hub via a web API which will be provided by SEI. In the Data Fabric frontend, it will be possible to hover over specific terms, e.g. “SSP scenario”, and see an explanation of the term including ‘scope notes’. The content will be fetched directly from the Connectivity Hub API. This ensures explanations are always up-to-date and allows to quickly add new terms. The terms which should be “hoverable” will be agreed on by involving all relevant project partners and stakeholders. Integrating data from the Connectivity Hub will provide important context information and make sure that the data and models can be understood and used properly.

2.7 Data Authorization, Authentication and Stewardship

Managing access and usage restrictions of data and services is an important cross-cutting concern of the Data Fabric. The reasons to restrict access are manifold and reach from not yet published data, to sensitive, i.e. safety relevant, data. To avoid the impact of unintended use or even misuse of available data, authentication and authorization components provide technical barriers to protect such data, services, and model outputs.

Storing personal data is an integral part of authentication and authorization, as it relies on permissions assigned to a user (directly or indirectly). However, the relevant information of a user will be kept at a minimum (i.e., name, email-address). This data is not a high risk to the rights and freedom of natural persons. Therefore, conducting a data protection impact assessment as described in D5.3 is not necessary.

During the development of the Data Fabric, the following aspects are considered:

- The accessing application acting on behalf of some user
- Well-known authentication protocols and standards
- Definition and enforcement of accessing restriction via policies

Revisiting the architecture overview from D5.1 (see [Figure 11](#)), the authentication and authorization component runs separately from the individual services proxied by the SDI gateway (see [Section 2.1](#)). Together with the gateway, the configuration of policy enforcement becomes centralised and easier to be managed by administrators and Data Stewards. Users, roles and groups can be created and reused over a set of policies and services. Once a user is authenticated (via OAuth2) and a valid access token has been provided, the following access to the actual data collections are granted (or not) per-request base.

Policies are defined by the Data Stewards, who are dedicated staff members that can add data sources and model configurations and control the access rights to models and data sets. Policies may be as simple as doing request parsing, but may get more complex when response filtering is required. Such filtering can be realised either with a simple request rewrite or by parsing and filtering the response. In case request rewriting is not possible (setting appropriate query filters transparent to the user) it may become a performance bottleneck quickly. Response filtering would then be better implemented by the individual service. However, serving particular subsets of the requested data was no requirement of any RWL so the centralised enforcement has been prioritised.

The definition of policies is part of the publication process (see [Section 2.4](#)). The result is a formal description document (policy) which can be interpreted by the policy enforcement component. The Data Fabric can support Data Stewards by providing predefined policy templates, for example for a dedicated audience:

- Public
- Owner only
- Members of a RWL
- All DIRECTED members

Within DIRECTED, the authorization component aims at further tooling to make writing access policies as easy as possible.

Figure 11: Technical Overview of the Data Fabric with its two core parts: The AuthZ component (left) that manages access by enforcing policies. The SDI components (right) that allow to find, access and process data relevant in the DIRECTED Data Fabric. The Data Steward has a central role in both component sets.

2.8 Applications

As described in the previous sections, the Data Fabric will offer access to a multitude of data and models. In order to enable their practical use by heterogeneous groups of stakeholders, it is necessary to provide suitable applications allowing them to view and interact with the data and models. While data visualisation and user interaction will be heavily influenced by and designed for the RWLs as further specified in [Section 3](#), in this section the different avenues in which the RWLs could potentially choose according to their stakeholders needs will be discussed. The following list gives a general overview of options, which will be explained in more detail afterwards (the numbers are not meant as ranking):

1. GIS layers which can be integrated into existing software solutions
2. Jupyter Notebooks
3. Customised web applications including, e.g., data dashboards or maps
4. Story maps
5. Existing solutions like SaferPlaces

(1) Geographic information systems (GIS) are software applications with a user interface - either a desktop or web-based user interface - capable of executing geospatial processes as well as visualising data as layers on top of a basemap. Stakeholder groups have noted that GIS systems are oftentimes too complex for them to use, and not easily used in times of emergency. As GIS needs to be run with user knowledge, this is understandable; however, storing GIS layers for future reference could still be an advantage within the DIRECTED project. The layers could then flexibly be integrated into widely used GIS software like QGIS or ArcGIS or into systems already developed by stakeholders of the RWL, e.g. the HORA platform in the Danube Region RWL. Thus, one option for data visualisation is to have GIS layers available via OGC standards served by, e.g., pygeoapi or GeoServer allowing further analysis or visualisation of project results outside the Data Fabric.

(2) Jupyter Notebooks are a way to run processes step-by-step in order to achieve some end goal. In addition, it is possible to mix in documentation or instructions in a visually appealing way or even to add widgets for user interaction or dynamic display of data. In the context of data visualisation, this could mean that users could go through the code of CLIMADA for simulating high levels of precipitation and storm surge in Roskilde Fjord, and viewing the flood map at the end of the notebook, displayed, potentially, as a layer on a Leaflet map. This would also provide a tool to contribute to the e-learning components of the DIRECTED project. However, Jupyter-Notebooks only target the rather skilled modeller willing to assess a pre-scripted analysis.

(3) Customised web applications could be built, tailored to the needs of the RWLs. These could include maps or data dashboards. Data dashboards can be standalone, or they could be linked to a map by providing detailed information about either a) a set region, point, or boundary in the map, or b) information based on parameters that a user sets. Depending on

the user requirements, data can also be displayed at any timescale which is feasible from the data source. For example, ECMWF offers seasonal forecasts available at a daily and sub-daily (6h) update frequency. If a variable from this dataset, such as precipitation, is specified by the end-user that they would like to visualise, a dashboard would be a beneficial way to display the values of precipitation at points or locations the user clicks in a web map. Web applications can be built using a wide range of programming languages, libraries and frameworks (e.g. React, Angular, Open Pioneer Trails, Streamlit, PyShiny). Some general useful components independent of the RWLs are:

- a catalogue for data and processes: this will be a way for users to find data and processes helpful for their specific use cases. Options to filter by, e.g., format, topic or spatial and temporal extent and resolution should be included among other features which could be requested by the RWLs.
- a simple user interface for running models/model chains: models provided as processes via the OGC API Processes standard have to be triggered using an HTTP request. This could be a hurdle for non-expert users. A user interface which hides these technical parts and allows viewing and running models via clicking a button will therefore be helpful to open models to a broader user group.
- a simple user interface for Data Stewards to manage policies: defining policies to control access to data and processes needs some expert knowledge. Depending on who will take the role of a Data Steward, this could make it challenging. A user interface could support Data Stewards, here also providing templates for basic cases.

Discussions, especially with the Emilia-Romagna RWL, have further shown that there is a need for a web-based application supporting the coordination of volunteers during a disaster event.

(4) Story Maps are another type of visualisation that is a blend between a presentation and dynamic geographical information. Instead of showing a static map in a slide, for example, Story Maps enable the integration of web maps alongside static text or pictures to convey spatial information in more detail. This data visualisation could be valuable for dissemination or educational purposes, as it could enable the broader public to see a story about the data and Data Fabric elements as a whole without needing to have someone presenting it to them. Additionally, Story Maps could be used toward the end of the project within the consortium, to showcase the Data Fabric to the RWL stakeholders. Story Maps could be developed by software engineers similar to the customised web applications. However, there are also tools which allow you to create Story Maps with a user interface and supporting features like drag-and-drop (e.g. <https://mapstories.de/en>). This would enable the direct use by non-technical stakeholders and Data Stewards could add further Story Maps as needs arise.

(5) Another option is to set up existing solutions like SaferPlaces for the RWLs. SaferPlaces does not only provide models to simulate, e.g., flood events but also includes a sophisticated user interface which allows users to view and upload datasets and to trigger model runs.

Integrating existing tools is i.e. advantageous for trained expert users who need to have full control over the modelling chain.

The development of applications depends on the actual needs of the RWL stakeholders and will be done in a co-creation process. [Section 3](#) will present more details on the user needs. Mock-ups of visualisations will be presented in Deliverable D5.4, Implementation Documentation of the Data Fabric.

2.9 Deployment and Runtime

The project deploys its application infrastructure within an Open Telekom Cloud-managed (OTC) Kubernetes (k8s) cluster, specifically within a dedicated and isolated namespace to ensure security and management efficiency. The cluster is running in the German datacenter of the OTC, because of GDPR requirements (see D5.3 "Data Protection & Impact Assessment" for more details). Access to the cluster resources is governed through the Kubernetes API server combined with OTC's Identity and Access Management (IAM) user controls, restricting user permissions strictly to namespace maintenance activities. To protect sensitive data, storage classes employ encryption techniques to prevent data leakage. To add another layer of protection, only the necessary applications have exposure to the internet, while all other components are confined within the project's cluster and namespace. Additionally, network policies are established to manage access to pods that expose ports, and the default OTC firewall configuration restricts incoming connections solely to ports 80 and 443. Traffic is routed to application pods through a load balancer for optimal control and access management. Reliability is ensured through Kubernetes' Horizontal Pod Autoscaler and Node Autoscaler, which automatically adjust resources to maintain uptime as demand fluctuates.

The codebase of each application is hosted on GitHub, where repository access is controlled by defined user groups and the visibility settings that correspond with project requirements. Applications are containerized and published to Docker Hub, facilitating efficient and consistent deployment. The infrastructure relies on Infrastructure as Code (IaC), with dedicated repositories hosted on GitHub separate from application code. This approach reduces visibility, limits access, and centralises control, as all project-specific resources are encapsulated within a single namespace and managed using Kubernetes' Kustomization tool.

Automated pipelines (see [Figure 12](#)) are implemented through GitHub workflows, where tagging the application code initiates builds, image uploads, and security scans via Trivy. Critical build information, such as sensitive configuration values, is stored securely in GitHub repository secrets. Docker Hub and the infrastructure's GitHub repositories are directly integrated with these workflows, allowing updates and deployments to be triggered by commits to the namespace repository or application repository. Trivy is employed twice within the pipeline and during runtime through the k8s Trivy Operator, ensuring continuous security assessment (see D5.3, Section 3.3.2).

Monitoring and alerting are achieved via a Prometheus operator within the same Kubernetes cluster. External endpoint monitoring ensures fast and efficient alerting in case of any downtime of any application within the infrastructure. Alerts based on the monitored metrics are sent through communication channels such as Slack, email, and others.

Figure 12: Build Pipeline from code change by a developer until the application in the cluster is updated.

3 Real World Lab

Interoperability Use Cases

This section provides an overview of how the interoperability use-cases already sketched in Deliverable D5.1 have evolved. The realisation of the user stories will be facilitated based on the technical components described in the [Section 2](#). To ensure meeting the RWL needs, the implementation phase will further incorporate the RWL hosts and stakeholders in feedback loops.

For each RWL, we present the personas and user stories that have been identified through collaborative discussions and workshops with RWL hosts, stakeholders and the DIRECTED team. *Personas describe a synthetic person which is representative for a user group. This description helps to better understand and detail the requirements in the context of the user. The user stories summarise in compact form the aspects:

- **Who** wants to do/achieve something (role)?
- **What** does this persona want to do (goal)?
- **Why** does this user want it (benefit)?
- **How** does the persona envision to achieve it?

This schema deviates slightly from the classical pattern where “how” is not part of a typical user story. During the discussions with our RWL hosts and stakeholders, the four questions turned out to be more comprehensive.

Because requirements might be very broad and to make sure that the most important aspects can be implemented within the project, a prioritisation scheme is applied to the user stories (must have, should have, could have, won't have). Within regular agile sprint meetings, the progress will be tracked and compared to the documented user needs (see D5.4). Known limitations to the user stories in the scope of the DIRECTED project can also be seen alongside the priority; this is to give an overview of the possible challenges which could arise from data availability, and/or during the technical implementation of the modelling chain, to achieve the aforementioned requirements in each user story. To easier reference user stories each of them has a unique ID following the scheme: “US<no of RWL>.[V|Z]<no of user story>”. For RWL 3, user stories are further distinguished between Vienna (V) and Zala (Z).

*it should be noted that the “name” section of the personas tables is sometimes labeled as “n/a.” This is because some RWLs, such as the Emilia-Romagna RWL, have communicated with an individual directly about the input visualizations. However, in most cases, the needs and requirements have been conducted in interviews with RWL hosts and are thus the wishes of a number of stakeholders rather than a specific person or organization. This is at times also for privacy considerations.

3.1 RWL 1 - Copenhagen Capital Region, Denmark

The Copenhagen Capital Region, Denmark, RWL, with a focus area in the Roskilde Fjord, aims to bridge data and communication gaps between different agencies that are responsible for DRM and CCA in the Capital Region, as well as in the Roskilde Fjord. These include:

- 1) Five municipalities part of the EU Flood Directive
- 2) Three Emergency Management Service (EMS) districts/organizations (responsible for action plans, goals, and current visualisations of data)
- 3) The Danish Coastal Authority (provides data currently)
- 4) The Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI)
- 5) Other knowledge providers (e.g., the Police)

In order to achieve this, the Data Fabric has been presented as a way for these different actors to find centralized information regarding future climate projections, as well as simulations for adaptation measures, which could aid in DRM and CCA. The following personas and user stories describe the needs and requirements to achieve the overarching goal of this RWL, which have been discussed and reiterated in a mock-up presentation with the stakeholders of this RWL.

Personas

The following tables provide structured information on the personas used in this RWL.

Title	GIS Specialist
Name	Carl
Organisation	Municipality
Responsibility (in general)	If available at all the primary function is to assist the municipality in planning, whether climate adaptation or other, secondary to analyse flood information from DMI in a GIS and inform the municipal and EMS authorities in times of potential high precipitation and storm surge

Title	City Planner in the Roskilde Fjord
Name	Ella
Organisation	City (under the jurisdiction of the municipality)
Responsibility (in general)	<p>Planning, developing, and executing local climate adaptation plans and projects. Individual property owners are responsible to protect their individual property.</p> <p>City planning along the coast of Roskilde Fjord to prevent seawater intrusion in the area of Roskilde Fjord covered by the municipality. Coordination with others is not mandatory.</p>

Title	Municipal Employee
Name	Frida
Organisation	Municipality
Responsibility (in general)	Analyzing storm maps and data to send warnings to the EMS

Title	Local Emergency Management Service Manager
Name	Erik
Organisation	Emergency Management Service (EMS)
Responsibility (in general)	Local EMS Manager who aids with practical emergency management like stacking sandbags and handling watertubes.

User Stories

Title	US1.1 GIS Flood-Map Layers and Information Sharing among the Municipalities
Who?	Carl
What?	As a GIS user, I look at precipitation data and flood-maps within QGIS (or ArcGIS) to make inferences about upcoming weather forecasts and potential hazard events. As this information is not readily understandable to my colleagues when I am unavailable, I need a software that is understandable and accessible in a GIS or WebGIS platform for my colleagues for precipitation and storm-surge related data
Why?	This would help in times of my absence, so that my colleagues are able to view the information, and coordinate with neighbouring municipalities and EMS during potential hazard events (namely, high-precipitation and storm surge)
How?	I would like to have flood-maps containing data in real-time via DMI; ideally these would also be attached to a WebGIS dashboard so that a discharge hydrograph can be viewed alongside the data and current storm-surge boundaries/physical barriers. I would like this all to be in a centralized “data viewer.” <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Precipitation and sea level data in real-time for all municipalities • Streamflow in real-time for all municipalities • Precipitation statistics for all municipalities
Limitations	Data layers will indefinitely be made available in the front-end GUI
Priority	High

Title	US1.2 Open Source Models able to Couple Between Persistent Rainfall and High Water Levels in the Roskilde Fjord
Who?	Ella
What?	As someone who uses model outputs from DMI, I analyse rainfall data and water levels in the Roskilde Fjord, to identify potential persistent rainfall events and high water levels in the Roskilde Fjord; I do this to plan and execute local climate adaptation plans and projects. However, the current models we use are not open source and do not couple between these two weather phenomena, and I would like to utilise the models in DIRECTED to do so
Why?	This would help in planning efforts, because we would have a better picture of the severity of the potential hazard event. When these two weather phenomena occur, they have had disastrous effects in the past. Thus, having models that couple these events would mean that our warnings are more robust
How?	I would like the modelling chain containing the coupled precipitation and water level data to be run daily, and the outputs to be stored in our local server for historical reference. During particularly hazardous events, I would like to be able to run the DTU Damage-Cost Model on demand, to see the potential impact of the event. I would also use this data for my planning of permanent adaptation measures. I would like this all to be in a centralized “data viewer.”

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sea level historical in Halsnaes M., Lejre M. and Roskilde M. • Future climate scenario sea level in Halsnaes M., Lejre M. and Roskilde M. • Wave height in real-time for Halsnaes M., Lejre M. and Roskilde M. • Wave height historical for Halsnaes M., Lejre M. and Roskilde M. • Streamflow historical for all municipalities • Precipitation in real-time for all municipalities • Precipitation historical for all municipalities
Limitations	Still needs more reflection from stakeholders, and datasets to be used are still to be determined
Priority	Medium

Title	US1.3 Adaptation Measures for Storm Surge
Who?	Ella
What?	As someone who works for the city, I look at areas in which to place barriers along the coast of Roskilde Fjord to prevent storm surge flooding . However, some of the old infrastructure is in need of updating—due to unprecedented levels of storm surge, sea level rise, and coupled weather phenomena events due to Climate Change, past measures are no-longer feasible, and municipalities must shift their approach to DRM.
Why?	This would help the coastal towns along the Roskilde Fjord with river flooding, and save the cities money with regard to flooding which could be easily prevented
How?	<p>I would like to see flood simulations with and without physical barriers, both in the current state and with barriers taken away. I would like to see these simulation outputs in an interactive Web Map to show to our stakeholders/the governing bodies of the towns surrounding the Fjord. Furthermore, I would possibly like to have different weighted criteria of interest.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sea level historical in Halsnaes M., Lejre M. and Roskilde M. • Wave height historical for Halsnaes M., Lejre M. and Roskilde M.
Limitations	Criteria for the MCDM will be defined by the stakeholders/RWL and developed with CLIMADA
Priority	Medium

Title	US1.4 Near-Real-Time Certainty Maps with and without Emergency Response Measures
Who?	Erik
What?	As a volunteer for emergency management services, I respond to warnings sent out by the municipal authorities and respond during hazard events. However, the data currently used by DMI has been unreliable in the past, i.e. it is not accurate and we waste time and resources responding to events which do not actually occur. Additionally, data is not accessible from the police force. Thus, having uncertainty predictions/analysis would be very helpful in our planning efforts to see in which areas have a high certainty of needing response
Why?	Having readily-available certainty maps would be helpful for our response efforts, so that we know where to deploy resources (i.e., water tubes) when warnings are issued: and, to avoid placing resources in the wrong places. Additionally, it would help us know where to focus our efforts and divide-up volunteer response
How?	I would like to have certainty maps with and without adaptation measures. Having this analysis in near-real-time would also be helpful, because the accuracy of current model outputs has not been the most ideal in the past. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wave height and sea level in real-time for Halsnaes M., Lejre M. and Roskilde M. • Precipitation in real-time for all municipalities
Limitations	Low priority for stakeholders, possibly redirecting efforts toward MCDM
Priority	Low

Title	US1.5 Near-Real-Time Certainty Maps for Planning Efforts
Who?	Frida
What?	As a municipal employee, I send out warnings to the local EMS manager. However, data currently used by DMI has been unreliable in the past and warnings have not been accurate. Additionally, we need uncertainty maps for long-term planning with and without adaptation measures, preferably including different climate change scenarios.
Why?	Having readily available certainty maps would be helpful for the warnings and communications we have with the EMS in times of response, so that we are both on the same page. In terms of our planning efforts, uncertainty analysis would help us to decide where to put/take away adaptation measures such as seawater barriers.
How?	I would like to have uncertainty maps for the Roskilde Fjord to compare between different model outputs. I would also like these uncertainty maps to include climate change scenarios, as well as the preparedness measures (e.g. temporary flood barriers/ watertubes). Furthermore, I would also like certainty data in near-real-time, so that our communications with the EMS are streamlined, and at a higher accuracy than the maps we receive from DMI. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wave height and sea level in real-time for Halsnaes M., Lejre M. and Roskilde M.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Precipitation in real-time for all municipalities ● Sea level historical in Halsnaes M., Lejre M. and Roskilde M. ● Wave height historical for Halsnaes M., Lejre M. and Roskilde M.
Limitations	Low priority for stakeholders, possibly redirecting efforts toward MCDM
Priority	Low

Data

Data sources which could be utilised in the Copenhagen Capital Region, specifically targeted toward the Roskilde Fjord, are included in the table below. Base data sources which will be used as input into the SaferPlaces, RIM2D, and CLIMADA models in all modelling chains are not included in [Table 2](#), but rather the data sources which are applicable to this RWL.

Table 2: Potential models and data sources of interest for the RWL Capital Region of Denmark.

Model	Dataset	Variables of Interest	Spatial/Temporal Resolution
SaferPlaces	DMI Historical Sea Levels Observed in the Roskilde Fjord	sealev_dvr sealev_In sea_reg tw	unknown spatial res, Denmark/10min-hourly
	DMI Projected Sea Level Rise	water level and storm surge	unknown spatial res, Denmark/reference period 1981-2010
	Copernicus CMIP6 Climate Projections	total runoff precipitation	global/from 2015 to 2100 for SSP experiments (daily or monthly)
RIM2D	DMI Climate Atlas Precipitation Statistics	Translation needed, datasets in DMI directory	Unknown spatial resolution, Denmark/last known update 2024-06-06
SCALGO	DMI Climate Atlas Precipitation Statistics	Translation needed, datasets in DMI directory	Unknown spatial resolution, Denmark/last known update 2024-06-06
DTU Damage-Cost Model	DEM via DMI or NASA	n/a	n/a, Denmark, input upon model run

Components used from the Data Fabric

The following modelling chain in [Figure 13](#) gives an overview of the input data and model connections which will be used to fulfill the user requirements, described in the user stories and personas, for the Copenhagen RWL. On the left, the input data section includes data for the SaferPlaces model, RIM2D and/or SCALGO models, the CLIMADA model, and the DTU Damage-Cost Model. As the SaferPlaces model contains a parameter for extreme sea level to simulate pluvial flood forcing, this parameter will be used to feed data via DMI (i.e., historical sea levels observed in the Roskilde Fjord, and projected sea level rise) for the Roskilde Fjord into the model. To simulate pluvial flood forcing, the SaferPlaces model also requires hydraulic inundation via rainfall intensity and duration; this data will come from RIM2D model outputs. For RIM2D, precipitation statistics provided by DMI will be used for the rainfall data input to simulate hydraulic inundation in the Roskilde Fjord, and is thus included in the hydrological models component in the modelling chain. For climate scenario simulations, such as the SSPs or RCPs being discussed with the stakeholders of this RWL, the climate data input of the SaferPlaces model will be utilized for datasets such as Copernicus CMIP6 Climate projections, seen in [Table 2](#) above. Other inputs, such as OSM, Soil Infiltration Maps, and Building Footprints and Asset maps, are included in the modelling chain flowchart, however it should be noted are base data, and thus have already been described in D5.1 and will not be detailed in-depth in this document.

On the right side of [Figure 13](#), the inputs and outputs to achieve the impact assessment with the DTU Damage-Cost Model and CLIMADA is shown. The CLIMADA model takes impact, hazard, and exposure as inputs to calculate the impact assessment. The hazard layer is defined as a 2D map of hazard intensity per event with a single variable, and will come from the SaferPlaces model. The exposure layer is defined as values at any geographical location, and must be compatible with geopandas (i.e., not a raster). This input will be provided via OSM. The impact layer is a function, or more specifically, a vulnerability curve; this layer relates to the percentage of damage in the exposure layer to the hazard intensity, and in the case of the Copenhagen RWL, will be calibrated based on the DTU Damage-Cost model. Finally, the impact assessment will come as an output of the CLIMADA model, where economic and climate impacts will be viewable as output. Additionally, the DTU Damage-Cost model will provide asset damages per sector (with sectors viewable in the GUI to be determined by the stakeholders). The CLIMADA model has also been discussed as a way to view uncertainty within the modelling chain outputs; this idea is also under discussion with stakeholders, however would take the same inputs as can be seen in the current modelling chain ([Figure 13](#)).

Figure 13: Modelling chain for RWL 1 in Emilia-Romagna.

One additional modelling approach with CLIMADA to view the impacts of adaptation measures is using a Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) assessment. This approach will also be under review with stakeholders in the next coming months in preparation for a workshop, to define the criteria which could be of most interest to stakeholders. For simplicity purposes with the many criteria possible, this assessment has not been included in the modelling chain; however, would also take the same inputs as currently shown in [Figure 13](#).

3.2 RWL 2 - Emilia-Romagna

Region, Italy

The Emilia-Romagna RWL contribution to developing the Data Fabric builds upon the high-level interoperability architecture outlined in D5.1, specifically focusing on Disaster Risk Management (DRM) and Climate Change Adaptation (CCA), expanding on the technical details of the interoperability framework, emphasising envisaged practical applications in the Emilia-Romagna Region. Through the Data Fabric's integration with local tools and systems, monitored real-time data, and models like pygeoapi and cloud-based infrastructures such as AWS, the deliverable outlines how the tools can be leveraged to meet stakeholder requirements.

Stakeholder feedback from workshops and meetings (e.g., March 2023 in Bologna, September 2023 in Ferrara) highlighted the need for improved forecasting capabilities and real-time flood monitoring. The Emilia-Romagna Data Fabric use-case applies these inputs by focusing on improving coordination between forecasting tools, hazard monitoring platforms, and multi-stakeholder decision-making processes (D1.1 Updated_DIRECTED_R...)(D5_1_High_Level_Design...).

The Real World Lab (RWL) 2 Emilia-Romagna is focused on supporting different users in both flood and wildfire risk reduction in two distinct locations: Rimini Province and Municipality of Mesola and Comacchio.

Concerning the RWL 2 needs for flood and wildfire risk reduction and adaptation, user needs, personas, and user stories are summarised as follows:

Personas

RWL 2 - Pluvial and Coastal Flood in Rimini Province

Title	Regional Civil Protection Officer
Name	Antonio/Christian
Organisation	Civil Protection at regional level
Responsibility (in general)	In case of potential pluvial and coastal flood events, they inform (early warning) and coordinate with municipal Civil Protection Officers for effective engagement and participation in disaster response and preparedness. Plans mitigations such as physical barriers and volunteer coordination.

Title	Municipal Civil Protection Officer
Name	Pietro
Organisation	Civil Protection at municipality level
Responsibility (in general)	Coordination of volunteers for Disaster Risk Reduction during a flood event. Support early warning and emergency operation. Coordinate the design of the Municipal Civil Protection Plan and Climate Change Adaptation.

RWL 2 - Wildfire in Mesola and Comacchio

Title	Regional Civil Protection Officer
Name	Clarissa
Organisation	Civil Protection at regional level
Responsibility (in general)	In case of potential wildfire events, they inform and coordinate with municipal Territorial Protection Officers for effective engagement and participation in disaster response and preparedness. Plans mitigations such as barriers and volunteer coordination.

Title	Territorial Civil Protection Officer
Name	Annamariaand Alceste
Organisation	Civil Protection at municipality level
Responsibility (in general)	Coordination of volunteers for Disaster Risk Reduction during a wildfire event. Support near-real-time and emergency operation. Coordinate the prevention and communication strategies.

User Stories

RWL 2 - Pluvial and Coastal Flood in Rimini Province

Title	US2.1 Early Warning and Disaster Risk Management (Municipal Civil Protection Agency)
What?	As a regional civil protection officer, I need a rapid flood modelling tool and interoperable web platform that integrates real-time data (both nowcasting sensors, radar and sea/weather forecasts) to produce high resolution data of near-real-time and short term forecast of pluvial and coastal flood events.
Why?	This helps in improving disaster preparedness and deploying resources more effectively. For example, designing and localising physical protection barriers or managing the volunteers properly.
How?	The forecasts should be communicated through ... maps/time series/traffic lights/calendar widget/... In an existing system, a newly developed web application?
Limitations	
Priority	High

Title	US2.2 Flood Resilience and Climate Change Adaptation (Municipal Civil Protection Agency)
What?	As a municipal civil protection officer, I need a platform capable of mapping flood hazards and damage, considering historical and projected climate data
Why?	This supports my work in adapting the civil protection plans to future climate conditions - Municipal Civil Protection Plan
How?	A cloud web app able to quickly generate flood scenario in a changing climate and changing urban environment
Limitations	
Priority	Middle

RWL 2 - Wildfire in Mesola and Comacchio

Title	US2.3 Disaster Risk Management (Territorial Civil Protection Agency)
What?	As a local civil protection officer, I need a rapid wildfire modelling tool and interoperable web platform that integrates real-time data (both nowcasting sensors and weather forecasts) to produce high resolution data of near-real-time and short term forecast of wildfire evolution.
Why?	This helps in improving disaster preparedness and deploying resources more effectively. For example, designing and localising physical protection barriers or managing the volunteers properly.
How?	The forecasts should be communicated through ... maps/time series/traffic lights/calendar widget/... In an existing system, a newly developed web application?
Limitations	
Priority	High

Data

The primary challenges in effective flood management in the RWL revolve around three critical areas:

- **Real-time, High-Resolution Flood modelling:** A significant hurdle is the need to reduce the latency of data from ARPAE (Regional Agency for Prevention, Environment and Energy of Emilia-Romagna) to enable real-time, high-resolution flood modelling. This is crucial for providing timely and accurate predictions of flood events, allowing for more effective and proactive responses.
- **Effective Communication and Governance:** Establishing seamless communication channels and robust governance frameworks between civil protection teams and the general citizenry is paramount. This ensures that vital information regarding flood risks and emergency procedures is disseminated efficiently, and that collaborative efforts can be effectively coordinated during and after flood events.
- **Climate Change Adaptation:** Addressing the profound impact of climate change in areas susceptible to flooding is a long-term and complex challenge. This involves developing and implementing strategies that enhance resilience to increased frequency and intensity of flood events, requiring comprehensive planning and sustainable solutions.

The following data sources will be used to enhance flood resilience:

To overcome these challenges, a multifaceted approach is proposed, focusing on technological advancements, community engagement, and accessible information:

- **Data Near-Real-Time and Forecasting from ARPAE:** A core solution involves optimizing data acquisition and forecasting capabilities from ARPAE to achieve near-real-time data flow. This improved data stream is fundamental for feeding into advanced flood models.

- **Integration of High-Resolution Models:** The integration of sophisticated high-resolution models, such as SaferPlaces and RIM2D, with real-time data is essential. This synergy allows for highly accurate simulations of flood scenarios, providing detailed insights into water flow, depth, and inundation areas. This integration is crucial for informing emergency responses and long-term planning.
- **Workshops and Co-Production Processes:** Fostering collaboration through workshops and co-production processes involving both citizens and municipalities is vital. This participatory approach ensures that local knowledge and community needs are incorporated into flood management strategies, leading to more relevant and widely accepted solutions. It also builds trust and empowers communities to take an active role in their own safety.
- **Simplified Web-GIS Applications:** The development and deployment of user-friendly Web-GIS (Geographic Information System) applications are critical for enabling easy data access and visualization. These applications democratize access to crucial flood-related information, allowing citizens, authorities, and stakeholders to readily understand risks, monitor situations, and make informed decisions. The simplified interface ensures accessibility for a broad range of users, regardless of their technical expertise.

The architecture of the RWL 2 Data Fabric shown in the diagrams aims to integrate real-time data, flood modelling, and hazard mapping, addressing user needs for Disaster Risk Management and Climate Change Adaptation.

Components used from the Data Fabric

1. Data Ingestor and Data Pre-Processing:

- Handles real-time observations from HERA radar, ARPAE open data (e.g., river levels, rainfall intensity, sea wave data), and various nowcasting data.
- Integrates with ARPAE Forecast Models (e.g., ICON, COSMO2I, COSMO5M) for weather and sea forecasts.
- Data sources include S3 Bucket Static Data (LIDAR, census data, land use, lithology) and external APIs for data from stakeholders and global datasets (e.g., Copernicus CDS):
 - Real-Time Data/Observation:
 - The starting point for collecting live data from various sources.
 - HERA/ARPAE/DPC Radar Data:
 - Related to radar systems providing precipitation or atmospheric data.
 - ARPAE Open Data:
 - Open data provided by ARPAE (possibly a meteorological agency).
 - River Level:
 - Data on river levels with hourly updates, useful for flood prediction.
 - Radar Rainfall Intensity:

- Provides real-time rainfall intensity maps or data feeds.
- Sea Wave Data:
 - Updated every 30 minutes, offering critical insights into sea conditions.
- Rain Gauge Stations:
 - Hourly updates on rainfall measurements from specific stations.
- Tidal Gauge Stations:
 - Provides tidal information, updated every 30 minutes.

2. PyGEOAPI Models - processes:

- An API that connects modelling tools like SaferPlaces, RIM2D, CLIMADA, and SVI (social vulnerability index) with real-time and static data.
- Produces high-resolution flood maps and hazard assessments that are accessible through a web platform.
- Forecast Models:
 - Weather Forecast (COSMO 1 and COSMO 5):
 - Two forecast models for weather, likely differing in resolution or scale.
 - Sea Forecast (SWAN/ADRIAC):
 - A model used for forecasting sea conditions.
 - Beach Profile Forecast:
 - Focuses on predicting changes to coastal profiles, possibly due to erosion or storm events.

3. K8s Orchestrator:

- Coordinates data flow between the ingesting processes, modelling tools, and the visualisation platform.
- Ensures interoperability and real-time updates of hazard maps and forecasts for users.

4. Visualisation Web Platform:

- A web-based GIS-like application providing:
- Maps and plots for rainfall intensity, sea level, and hazards (pluvial and coastal).
- Options to add flood mitigation measures such as barriers and simulate multiple mitigation scenarios.

Figure 14: Flow chart of data, processes and results for the RWL Emilia-Romagna Region.

The architecture addresses key user stories, such as those of civil protection officers and municipal authorities, by providing the necessary tools for real-time flood management, hazard mapping, and Climate Change Adaptation in a user-friendly, interoperable platform.

3.3 RWL 3 - Danube Region, Vienna, Austria, and Zala Region, Hungary

3.3.1 Vienna

The Vienna, Austria, portion of the Danube RWL aims to bring together stakeholders within the insurance industry, and the public and science sectors, as cross-communication between these actors in Austria is currently limited or not present. The Data Fabric will thus be a way to centralize climate information within the city of Vienna, in terms of early warning and realistic disaster scenarios, as well as by encouraging cross-border communication, as reinsurance industry actors in Austria also often span over national borders.

Within the following personas and user stories, insurance industry actors, representatives in the science industry, and countries within the Danube River Basin, have been discussed as example target user groups of the Data Fabric, in order to develop the tools and infrastructure that can encourage data sharing and communication in all respective sectors.

Personas

Title	Climate Reinsurance Representative
Name	Malte
Organisation	Hannover Reinsurance Company
Responsibility (in general)	To analyse data provided by platforms such as HORA to gain information on early-warning and potential hazard events for reinsurance claims.

Title	Climate Insurance Representative
Name	Achim
Organisation	UNIQA Insurance Group, Vienna
Responsibility (in general)	To look at climate forecasting models and scientific papers published to inform UNIQA on potential insurance claims related to pluvial and fluvial flooding in Vienna (with a focus on pluvial flooding, as the weir system in Vienna currently protects the city from overflows from the Danube).

Title	Climate Scientist
Name	Markus
Organisation	Geosphere Austria
Responsibility (in general)	Providing up-to-date information on climate models and adapting modules within the Geosphere Austria platform.

Title	Citizen
Name	Berthold
Organisation	n/a
Responsibility (in general)	As a current citizen of Vienna, knowing the risk of natural disasters (e.g. floods) helps to get prepared and take mitigation measures. As a potential future citizen of Vienna, knowing which areas of the city are prone to floods is important when moving or buying a house.

Title	Asset holder (shops/houses)
Name	Helmuth
Organisation	Private or corporate
Responsibility (in general)	As a (potential future) asset holder, understanding the financial risks to assets helps to make decisions (e.g. insurance contracting, new investments or disinvestments).

Title	Employee of local municipality
Name	Michael
Organisation	Municipal department 45 (MA45) - "Wiener Gewässer" (water management)
Responsibility (in general)	Water bodies in Vienna

Title	Corporate risk manager
Name	Stefan
Organisation	Viadonau (waterway operator)
Responsibility (in general)	Flood and crisis management along the Danube in Austria

Title	Farmer
Name	Arnd
Organisation	n/a
Responsibility (in general)	Keeping cattle on pastures along the Danube and/or growing livestock feed on fields along the Danube. Understanding flood risks helps to take preparational actions and to make decisions, e.g. where to build a barn.

Epics

Title	EPIC3.V1 Enrichment of the public-private HORA flood risk assessment web platform by including DIRECTED technology
Description	The HORA platform (Natural Hazard Overview & Risk Assessment Austria, https://www.hora.gv.at) is well adopted in Austria and can be regarded as a “best practice”. Enriching it with DIRECTED technology could benefit its users. Furthermore, it would increase the visibility of the DIRECTED project.
Limitations	An integration of DIRECTED data/technology into HORA will not be possible due to organizational and legal restrictions. However, the stakeholders are interested in the DIRECTED results - especially those related to pluvial flooding. Thus, the user stories associated with this Epic (US3.V1-US3.V3) are still valid.

User Stories

Title	US3.V1 Pluvial flood modelling in urban areas
EPIC	EPIC3.V1
Who?	All personas
What?	Integration of high resolution pluvial flood modelling in urban areas (Vienna).
Why?	In Vienna, there is a comprehensive fluvial flood defence system, to take in flood waters from the Danube River. However, pluvial flooding still remains an issue. Thus, the DIRECTED consortium models could contribute to the pluvial flood data landscape within Vienna.
How?	Hazard (pluvial flood) from SaferPlaces and/or RIM2D and impact assessment outputs from SaferPlaces and/or CLIMADA could be provided via OGC standards (OWS, OGC APIs) by the Data Fabric and integrated into the HORA platform. Alternatively, the models could be run on demand via a processing web API.
Limitations	The Data Fabric will only run as long as the DIRECTED project. If the data and services from the project should be available in HORA afterwards, a (commercial) strategy needs to be developed by all relevant parties. This strategy also needs to incorporate ethical aspects, e.g. open access or how layers can be updated if the determining factors, i.e. input of the models, change.
Priority	High priority

Title	US3.V2 Fluvial flood modelling upstream and downstream of Vienna
EPIC	EPIC3.V1
Who?	All personas
What?	Fluvial flood modelling in the northwest and southeast of Vienna.
Why?	In Vienna, there is a comprehensive fluvial flood defence system, to take in flood waters from the Danube River. However, there is a risk of river flooding upstream and downstream of Vienna.
How?	Fluvial flood modelling outputs from the Danube model could be provided via OGC standards (OWS, OGC APIs) by the Data Fabric and integrated into the HORA platform.
Limitations	The Data Fabric will only run as long as the DIRECTED project. If the data and services from the project should be available in HORA afterwards, a (commercial) strategy needs to be developed by all relevant parties. This strategy also needs to incorporate ethical aspects, e.g. open access or how layers can be updated if the determining factors, i.e. input of the models, change.
Priority	Middle priority

Title	US3.V3 Climate projections of flood risk
EPIC	EPIC3.V1
Who?	All personas
What?	Analyse how fluvial and pluvial flood risks change with different climate projections.
Why?	Improve risk assessment, have better predictive analytics and inform mitigation.
How?	Combination of Danube Model and CLIMADA. We could choose two scenarios, e.g. SSP370 and SSP585.
Limitations	Limited spatial resolutions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Climate scenario data (ISIMIP): 0,5° (ca 50 km), daily data of ten realizations per scenario (SSP370 and SSP585) until 2100 available • The weather input to calibrate the Danube Model is at 0.1° (ca 10 km). • Flood data: 100 m for downscaled fluvial flooding from the Danube Model; the original modelling resolution is 3 arc minutes (ca 5 km).
Priority	Middle priority

Title	US3.V4 (Selected) Natural Hazard Overview for the Danube River Basin
Who?	All personas
What?	The integration of countries outside Austria, i.e. within the Danube River Basin, into a HORA-like platform for sharing data and information on natural hazards (precalculated hazard maps) focusing on fluvial floods and drought with a potential extension to wind.
Why?	The HORA platform is well adopted in Austria and can be regarded as a “best practice”. Thus, extending it to other countries in the Danube River Basin could be beneficial for supporting DRM and CCA.
How?	Application of DIRECTED consortium models to countries in the Danube basin and collection of (public) data. The Danube Model could be used for river flooding and droughts. CLIMADA could be used for cost-damage analyses. As RIM2D and SaferPlaces are used to create high resolution maps it might not be feasible to apply them to larger areas. Data on wind hazards might be publicly available. Model outputs and additional data could be presented in a map-centered web application.
Limitations	Cloning all functionalities of the HORA platform for the whole Danube basin is far out of scope of the DIRECTED project. This system would be limited by the modelling capabilities within the project consortium and by the availability of data. In line with the project scope, a HORA-like system could also be restricted to the Zala (West Balaton) Region.
Priority	Low priority (more a follow-up work after the project)

Title	US3.V5 HORA-like Tool for “Nearcasting” and Early Warning in the Danube River Basin
Who?	Climate Reinsurer at Hannover Reinsurance Company
What?	I would like to see a platform similar to HORA which includes weather forecasts and building asset damages at a city-level; having a dashboard/legend which also includes model comparison would also be quite interesting, as we do not communicate adequately with the science industry.
Why?	As a climate reinsurer at Hannover Reinsurance Company, I analyse data provided by platforms such as HORA to inform the company about potential reinsurance claims. However, to gain this information, I oftentimes have to search through multiple different platforms and databases to get climate information about the entire river basin, especially in regard to extreme weather (i.e. convective storms and flooding events). As such, I need a centralised platform similar to HORA, that spans across multiple EU countries and across the Danube River Basin.
How?	Integrating data from the European Flood Awareness System (EFAS) and/or the Global Flood Awareness System (GloFAS) might be an applicable way to fulfill some requirements of this user story. The requirement of integrating forecast data also exists in the RWL Emilia-Romagna Region, thus, it might be possible to reuse components/results from there.
Limitations	The user story depends on the availability of (suitable) forecast data for the desired area.
Priority	Low priority

Title	US3.V6 Climate Forecasts for Pluvial Flooding in Vienna
Who?	Climate Insurer at UNIQA Insurance Group, Vienna
What?	I would like a platform which gets information from sound climate models and can model pluvial flooding in the city of Vienna. I would like to see this information at a daily time-step, with forecasts in the next 72 hours, and future climate predictions for a 100 year flood statistic. I would like to be able to see building asset damages for all these forecasts. Ideally, these results would be displayed in an interactive WebGIS, and be able to print out a pdf of the flood maps for internal documentation.
Why?	As a climate insurer, I look at scientific papers and forecasting models to look at potential hazard events, particularly with regard to pluvial flooding. I need a way to centralise this information, because sifting through up-to-date scientific papers and forecasting models can be time-consuming and difficult to get a clear picture from.
How?	This user story is similar to US3.V1 but adds the requirement of forecasting. The same models could be used, however, run with different input data.
Limitations	The user story depends on the availability of (suitable) forecast data for the desired area.
Priority	Low priority (possible extension of US3.V1)

Title	US3.V7 Centralised Platform for Information Sharing between the Insurance and Science Sectors in Austria
Who?	Climate Scientist at Geosphere Austria
What?	I would like to have a way to compare our climate models with the information the insurance industry uses, ideally in a centralized platform containing their climate model outputs and some of the ones that we host ourselves. I would also like a way to communicate with various actors in said platform.
Why?	As a climate scientist at Geosphere Austria, I look at climate models and adapt the platform so that our information is robust and up-to-date. However, a lot of the information that we release on the platform has little to no connection with the insurance industry, which makes it difficult to inform citizens (i.e., there is an information mismatch that makes communicating climate risk difficult). Thus, I need a way to communicate climate information with insurance companies in Austria. This would help to bridge the gap between science and the insurance industry for everyday citizens.
How?	-
Limitations	Developing a (new) platform for the science and insurance sectors is far out of scope of the DIRECTED project. What the project can do is provide recommendations and best practices in terms of technological and organizational solutions, especially when it comes to interoperability.
Priority	Low priority

Data

[Table 3](#) details data sources which could be utilised in the Danube, Vienna, RWL. As mentioned previously, base data sources and descriptions can be found in D5.1, with the table below showing data sources which are applicable to this RWL.

Table 3: Potential data sources of interest for the Danube, Vienna, RWL.

Model	Dataset	Variables of Interest	Spatial/Temporal Resolution
SaferPlaces	Copernicus CMIP6	Precipitation, total runoff	Global/from 2015 to 2100 for SSP experiments
RIM2D	ECMWF seasonal forecasts	Total precipitation	Global/subdaily (6h) and daily
	EFAS E-Hype Model Precipitation Forecasts	River discharge	Europe/January 2021-present with 7 month lead time, daily or monthly
	ERA5 near-real-time precipitation	Convective rain rate (rainfall intensity)	Global/hourly

In addition, the following wish list of parameters for different categories of data were communicated by the stakeholders.

Meteorological parameters

- Precipitation amount (total precipitation in mm)
- Precipitation intensity (rain rate in mm/h)
- Duration and frequency of heavy rainfall events
- Snowmelt (temperature-dependent, influences spring flooding)

Hydrological parameters

- Soil moisture before a rainfall event
- Groundwater level (influences runoff behaviour)
- River levels and discharge rates
- Catchment size and topography (influences water drainage)
- Soil infiltration capacity (e.g., sandy soil vs. clay soil)

Geophysical parameters

- Terrain topography and elevation profile (e.g., digital elevation models, DEM)
- Degree of sealing of surfaces (cities have a higher risk of flooding)

Infrastructure and risk parameters

- Presence of flood protection measures (dams, dikes, retention basins)
- Discharge capacity of sewer systems
- Density of buildings and property values in floodplains
- Historical flood data and damage records

Components used from the Data Fabric

[Figure 15](#) shows an overview of the modelling chain for the Danube, Vienna, RWL. Models which have been identified as applicable to the needs of this RWL include the SaferPlaces, Danube, and RIM2D models. In order to fulfill the requirement to enrich the HORA platform for flood-risk assessment, climate forecasts from various providers such as EFAS, ECMWF, and Copernicus (ERA5), will be utilized as input into the models to produce the hydraulic inundation output needed for the SaferPlaces rainfall flood forcing parameter. This will be done for the city of Vienna, and possibly for other urban areas in the Danube Region per stakeholder requests (such as, for example, the partner country of this RWL in Hungary). The SaferPlaces model will then use these inputs for an impact assessment, whereby damage incurred by a fluvial flood will be made available via pygeoapi and/or GeoServer for integration by representatives at HORA. As the climate data from the providers listed above is also available at near-real-time, this modelling chain framework could also be made available at this time-scale for the HORA platform integration.

To fulfill the GUI requirements for a “best-practice” HORA platform, outputs from the Danube Model will be utilized for the drought aspects in the Danube River Basin. This data will be integrated alongside components used within the HORA platform, so that other countries in the Danube River Basin can view drought impacts, as well as possible flooding scenarios from SaferPlaces and RIM2D.

Figure 15: modelling chain overview for the Danube, Vienna, RWL.

3.3.2 Zala Region

The Zala Region, Hungary, part of the Danube RWL aims to bring together stakeholders within the Western Balaton part of the region, namely in the City of Keszthely, and volunteer organizations, which are prevalent in the response phase to natural hazards in the region. The Data Fabric in the Zala Region will serve as a means to give climate information to citizens and governmental bodies alike, in order to showcase insights about climate uncertainties, so that stakeholders in the region are better able to make climate informed decisions.

While this part of the lab is less focused on the response-phase of natural hazards, the hope is that this lab is able to gain information and learning tools from the other RWLs, with regard to response, to make CCA and DRM more feasible in the future. Communication and motivation of stakeholders has been mentioned as challenging in this region due to cultural differences, and thus the following user stories were created to meet these differences, while still maintaining the overarching goals of the DIRECTED project.

The data, models and analyses for the Zala Region showcase the EU's local-level preparedness framework at the **LAU1 and LAU2 levels** (micro-region, geographical units, and municipal level). These outputs can be leveraged for public engagement but also provide examples of how concepts like the sponge city approach could be adapted, particularly in small towns. They aim to encourage a **preventive approach** at the local governance level by promoting the more efficient use of local financial resources and ensuring the resilience of local public services.

The complexity of the region arises from **several interconnected factors**. Poor agricultural practices in certain areas, coupled with intensive cultivation, have led to the degradation of

the upper soil layer, resulting in muddy floods. These floods wash sediments into the Zala River and the filtration system of Lake Balaton, potentially damaging the region's water protection infrastructure. In addition, the challenges are compounded by significant tourism activities, the expansion of built-up areas, urban management pressures, and the need to safeguard designated conservation sites, including **Ramsar and Natura 2000 areas**, as well as forests, reed beds, and aquatic ecosystems. These combined pressures heighten the demand for preparedness, resilience-building, and decision-support systems to address the complex interplay of environmental, economic, and social factors.

Personas

Title	Members of the Water Board at Lake Balaton
Name	Zsófia(hydrologist, National Water Management Directorate General) and Viktor (biologist, Balaton Limnological Research Institute)
Organisation	National Water Management Directorate General
Responsibility (in general)	The National Water Management Directorate General at West-Balaton Region is responsible for the inland water ecosystem and management at the Lake. The two key organisations are working on improving safety measures along the lake (early warning system, management and maintenance of infrastructures designed to protect areas from hydrological risks, including dams, levees, floodgates, and other water control systems in Zala and the West-Balaton Region) The Balaton Limnological Research Institute plays a crucial role in addressing climate change by studying the impacts of environmental changes on freshwater ecosystems, particularly Lake Balaton and its surroundings. The institute conducts research on water quality, biodiversity, and ecological processes to understand how rising temperatures, changing precipitation patterns, and human activities influence aquatic habitats. Additionally, it develops strategies for sustainable water management, monitors invasive species, and provides data to inform policy decisions aimed at mitigating the effects of climate change on regional and global freshwater systems.

Title	Mayor (of Keszthely)
Name	Gergely
Organisation	Mayor of Keszthely
Responsibility (in general)	The Mayor of Keszthely has several key responsibilities, including representing the city in official matters, leading the local government, and overseeing the implementation of municipal decisions. They are responsible for managing public services, ensuring compliance with local and national regulations, and fostering economic development within the city. Additionally, the mayor collaborates with the city council to develop policies and strategic plans, supervises the municipal budget, and acts as a liaison between residents and government authorities to address community needs effectively. The mayor can implement and support initiatives addressing climate change by promoting sustainable tourism practices, enhancing disaster preparedness and resilience measures, and ensuring social programs

	are in place to protect vulnerable populations from climate-related impacts. Situated on the shores of Lake Balaton, in eastern Zala County near the Zala River and the Kis-Balaton Region, Keszthely is particularly vulnerable to extreme weather events, including forest and bush fires in the Keszthely Hills due to invasive pine species, as well as reed fires in the extensive reed beds along the lakeshore.
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Title	Chief land manager
Name	Attila
Organisation	Bakony Forestry Company Plc.
Responsibility (in general)	Responsible for long-term planning of activities (10, 50, 100 years) e.g. in the West Balaton Region. The Bakony Forestry Company Plc. operates in the Bakony Region, encompassing a diverse area that includes forested hills, protected natural reserves, and parts of the Balaton Uplands, focusing on long-term sustainable forestry, wildlife management, and conservation efforts.

Title	Zala County Defence Committee, Secretary General /including voluntary organisations in Zala + relationship with municipalities
Name	Péter
Organisation	Zala County Defence Committee
Responsibility (in general)	<p>Responds to hazard events in the Zala Region, namely at a residential level.</p> <p>The Zala County Defence Committee is supporting local municipalities, NGOs and local authorities with disaster preparedness and response locally (e.g. sandbags, tree removal) and awareness raising (e.g. engagement in schools).</p> <p>This support is likely to increase and needs expansion of more resources in the future given increasing frequency and intensity of multiple climate and weather-related hazards.</p> <p>Opportunity to learn from other European countries through the Real World Lab knowledge exchange, e.g. Emilia-Romagna and Denmark. Opportunity to explore future scenarios (explore impacts/ measures) in workshops (starting with flooding, evolve to multi-hazard) and discuss how as voluntary organisations they need to adapt and explore how the collaboration with municipalities could evolve to support DRR and CCA.</p> <p>Workshops focus on engagement of cooperation with voluntary organisations (how can they become more resilient) and can be a starting point for deeper science-informed dialogue between municipalities and voluntary organisations on DRR/CCA. The risk communication products produced (e.g. risk maps, procedural workflows) can be used for this dialogue.</p>

Title	CEO
Name	Miklós
Organisation	National Chamber of Agriculture
Responsibility (in general)	This organisation represents the interests of agricultural producers, farmers, businesses, and stakeholders in Zala County, Hungary, providing support, advocacy, and resources for the agricultural sector.

Title	Pomologist, fruit breeder
Name	Gyula
Organisation	Carpathian Basin fruit gene bank
Responsibility (in general)	Gyulais the owner and the founder of the Pórszombat "Tündé kert" (Fairy Garden), the largest regional gene bank in the Carpathian Basin, preserving more than 2,000 native fruit tree varieties. He is also working on selecting resilient varieties from old fruit cultivars.

User Stories

Title	US3.Z1 Multi-hazard dashboard for Zala and West Balaton Region
Who?	Voluntary members of the Zala Special Rescue Team
What?	View multi-hazard maps (fluvial and pluvial flooding, drought, wildfires, storms) showing which hazards can be expected in the near future (seasonal and yearly forecasts) at a regional level. This tool should (help) predict the probability of occurrence.
Why?	<p>Support short-term (seasonal forecasts) and medium-term planning (up to approx. 30 years) within and across all voluntary organisations and local authorities for future extreme climate and weather-related events (fluvial and pluvial flooding, drought, wildfires, storms) in the West Balaton Region. Planning could mean, e.g., how many sandbags have to be stored where to prevent damage by floods.</p> <p>Encourage more bottom-up community-led Civil Protection connecting Disaster Risk Reduction and Climate Change Adaptation through stronger collaboration between voluntary organisations in the West Balaton Region to strengthen climate and disaster resilience.</p> <p>Understand how voluntary organisations can best prepare for and adapt to the impact of climate change on their emergency preparedness and response planning and actions, as well as their climate/disaster related outreach and awareness activities with the public/citizens.</p> <p>For example, understand if synergies can be captured through combining or sharing resources in the most impacted areas.</p> <p>Facilitate stronger collaboration with municipalities (to advocate for additional resources/needs) through enhanced access to risk</p>

	<p>communication products (e.g. risk maps).</p> <p>Such information is useful when applying for funds, consultations, agreements with the Ministry of Interior and local authorities on annual tasks, support tasks and voluntary capacity building.</p>
How?	<p>Flood model at city scale (SaferPlaces, Rim2D) and West Balaton scale, e.g. Zala river (Danube model).</p> <p>If a wildfire model (e.g. from DTU) will be available during the remaining time of the project, CLIMADA could be used for impact estimations/multi-criteria analysis for different future scenarios.</p> <p>Visualization of climate scenario data from ISIMIP (see “Data” section). Due to the spatial resolution only about 10 pixels cover the Zala and West Balaton Region.</p> <p>Visualization of seasonal forecasts from Copernicus and long-range forecasts from ECMWF. These datasets must be presented in a way that they are easy to understand.</p> <p>Visualize data on past disaster events on a map.</p>
Limitations	<p>Seasonal forecasts are of limited value, because dynamical modelling is not feasible with their general information (e.g. expecting spring precipitation 20% above average, but no information on date and location of eventual torrential rain events). However, they may help adjust the level of general risk awareness for specific hazards (e.g. increased wildfire danger in a drier-than-normal season).</p>
Priority	High

Title	US3.Z2 Multi-hazard dashboard at Municipal Level in the Western Balaton Region to Support Future Climate/Disaster Resilience
Who?	Mayor of the City of Keszthely and Hévíz (representing 280 mayors in the Zala Region)
What?	<p>Risk maps/simulations for future flooding (pluvial and fluvial) and future precipitation/temperatures (drought, wildfires, heat waves) at a municipal level.</p> <p>RWL learning exchange with examples (risk products/outputs) from other cities/regions (e.g. Denmark and Emilia-Romagna).</p>
Why?	<p>Ensure our city and the municipalities in the region are prepared for and can adapt to future extreme weather and climate extreme events and socio-economic impacts (flooding, drought, wildfires) with a focus on what we can do in our election cycle (5 years).</p> <p>To strengthen climate resilience of citizens and regional development sectors (economic growth and tourism).</p> <p>Future planning for elderly care: how does the extent of warming affect hospital load? Basically, it is sufficient if a model can show the average summer temperature level, as this alone can serve as an alert value - preferably displayed as heat waves if possible.</p> <p>Identify pathways to action - measures, resource distribution, governance -</p>

	<p>results/progress made are visible within 4-5 years.</p> <p>Increased use of funds, taxpayer’s money, government support for municipal development and public services in terms of climate resilience efficiency. Expanding tools for urban planning and local governance, managing local infrastructure.</p>
How?	Model chain/outputs would be the same as for the volunteer organisations (US3.Z1), with a focus on decision-making support at municipal level and the actions they can do in 5 years.
Limitations	See US3.Z1
Priority	High

Title	US3.Z3 Supporting regional fruit growers in variety selection and breeding.
Who?	Gyula, owner of the largest collection of traditional fruit varieties, pomologist . Gyula is a pomologist and the founder of the Pórszombat "Tündé kert" (Fairy Garden), the largest regional gene bank in Central-Europe, preserving more than 2,000 native regional fruit tree varieties.
What?	To understand the impacts of climate change and protect native fruit varieties, I need regional climate models that provide detailed insights into local climate changes, particularly temperature fluctuations, rainfall distribution, and the frequency of drought periods.
Why?	Native fruit varieties have adapted to the traditional climatic conditions of the Carpathian Basin, but climate change introduces new challenges. Accurate climate data helps me understand how these changes affect tree growth, fruit yield, and resilience, enabling more effective preservation and maintenance of this genetic heritage. Using climate model data, I can monitor temperature and rainfall changes and adjust fruit tree care and propagation methods accordingly. For example, if the models predict prolonged drought periods, I can implement irrigation and soil moisture retention techniques to support the trees' survival and health.
How?	Collection and visualization of (public) datasets.
Limitations	There are no suitable models for the temperature/precipitation/drought impacts on fruits in the consortium. The user story depends on the availability of public datasets for these phenomena. It was evaluated if the ABSOLUT crop yield model can be used/adjusted for fruits. However, there is not enough data on fruit yields on the regional scale. Eurostat has only national resolutions. The ABSOLUT crop yield model would need > 20 years of yield data from > 100 adjoining regions to run.
Priority	Low

Title	US3.Z4 Long-term crop yields
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Who?	Miklós(Chamber of Agriculture) representing the interest of farmers
What?	Understand how crop yields develop in future climate scenarios. Understand how precipitation will change in the next 50 to 100 years and if there will be more frequent/severe droughts.
Why?	Identify how to adapt my practices, e.g. planting of certain types of trees (possibly imported from abroad) or investing in an irrigation system.
How?	Crop yield outputs from the ABSOLUT model. The CLIMADA model might be used to study the uncertainty of crop yields.
Limitations	-
Priority	High/Medium

Title	US3.Z5 Long-term forest planning, Climate Change-related Forest Soil and Water Management
Who?	Attila, Bakonyerdő Forestry Company. The Bakonyerdő Forestry Company manages over 62,000 hectares of state-owned forestland, primarily located in Veszprém County, with smaller areas in Zala and Győr-Moson-Sopron Counties. Within this, it manages wildlife on approximately 60,000 hectares , across six hunting areas, in four regions, and three counties.
What?	Understand future climate scenarios. Understand how precipitation will change in the next 50 to 100 years and if there will be more frequent/severe droughts. Modelling the relationship between soil conditions and climate change in forested areas, focusing on soil water management and its impact on tree health. Issues such as drought-induced forest decline, the inability of native tree species to tolerate prolonged dry periods, and the need for better soil and water management strategies to ensure forest sustainability.
Why?	Identify how to adapt my practices, e.g. planting of certain types of trees (possibly imported from abroad) or investing in an irrigation system, natural water retention measures (NWRMs). Climate change has disrupted previously stable conditions (1960–1990), leading to consecutive drought years and forest degradation in areas like the Keszthely Hills. Native forests face challenges due to these changes, which affect soil water content, tree growth, and overall forest resilience. This requires innovative monitoring and management solutions to preserve biodiversity and forest health.
How?	Integrate climate projections of precipitation, e.g. the ISIMIP dataset. Potentially, a forest fire model might be used, e.g. ForeFire. The forestry has several local weather monitoring stations. Data from these stations could be integrated. Data and Monitoring: Utilize remote sensing technologies (e.g., NDVI) and in-situ soil moisture measurements to assess the impact of climate change on forest soil and tree conditions. Management Practices: Develop forestry strategies focused on soil water retention and adapt traditional forestry practices to new climatic realities based on modelling. modelling and Analysis: Integrate local soil and climatic data into

	<p>predictive models to guide decision-making and improve drought resilience. Collaboration: Promote knowledge sharing and data integration among forestry and agricultural stakeholders to address shared challenges.</p>
Limitations	<p>The availability of meaningful data sources is unclear. In the consortium, no models are available for simulating soil and climatic conditions in forests.</p>
Priority	<p>High (visualization of existing datasets; not everything described is feasible, see “limitations” section)</p>

Title	US3.Z6 modelling the water protection measures of the Kis-Balaton filtration system under prospective climate conditions.
Who?	Water management experts, agricultural professionals, conservationists, and local communities invested in protecting the Kis-Balaton catchment area
What?	<p>Developing flow and sediment transport models: Analyse water flow dynamics and sediment deposition, and create effective dredging models. Soil and erosion management: Implement measures to cover and protect the topsoil, and prevent sediment and debris from entering water systems. Upgrading infrastructure: Increase the capacity of wastewater treatment plant buffers and strengthen the embankments of fishponds. Drought resilience: Plan and design water reservoirs to combat drying trends while balancing ecological needs in protected areas. Collaboration and data sharing: Foster partnerships between stakeholders (e.g., scientists, conservationists, policymakers), exchange data on water quality and hydrology (e.g., 2020 flash flood data), and establish clear agreements for mutual benefit. Simulation of the condition assessment and load testing of critical water infrastructure and protective structures in the event of a flash flood. A significant flash flood occurred in 2020 – its lessons can be utilized, as the climatic conditions were recorded and the consequences were well-documented.</p>
Why?	<p>Climate change is causing increased soil erosion, droughts, flash floods, and algal blooms, which threaten the water quality, biodiversity, and agricultural stability of the Kis-Balaton area. Key issues include sediment accumulation, drying of the topsoil, extreme rainfall events, and insufficient buffer capacity of wastewater treatment plants and fishponds.</p> <p>The Kis-Balaton catchment area plays a vital role in maintaining Lake Balaton’s water quality, preserving natural habitats, and ensuring agricultural sustainability. Without timely interventions, the area’s water management system could fail, leading to environmental disasters such as pollution (like the DDT-related fish deaths) or habitat loss.</p>
How?	n/a
Limitations	Water flow could be modelled using SaferPlaces. There are no models for sediment transport available in the consortium.
Priority	Medium

Title	US3.Z7 Municipality Flood Risk Mapping & Mitigation Strategies to complement existing models
Who?	National General Directorate of Water Management (NGDWM) Mr. Örs Antal (hydrologist, modeller)
What?	Development of urban flood risk maps based on meteorological data, topography, land use, and drainage infrastructure to identify flood-prone areas and evaluate mitigation measures.
Why?	Flood risk mapping, which is our most important strategic project and is based on hydrodynamic modelling and risk calculations. The end product is flood and risk maps. We have modelling for both small rivers and larger rivers (floodplains): the descriptive sections and maps are available here: https://vizeink.hu/kezdolap-akk/ We are now in the process of the 2nd revision of the plan and maps, but we are crying for more complex aspects and more data to be incorporated in the risk calculations. On the logic of this, I suggested that similar risk reduction calculations could be done for municipal inland areas, perhaps as a gap filling exercise. For example, if meteorological data could be used to produce flash flood and urban flood risk maps for specific sample areas (cities, towns). This would require basic data such as topography, built-up areas, infrastructure elements, surface cover (paved, unpaved surfaces) and drainage network (water absorption, capacity, etc.). The knowledge of runoff (runoff catchment locations, with runoff depth data) could be used to investigate or model how different green infrastructure elements (e.g. green roofs, parks, rain gardens, etc.) or preventive solutions (e.g. retention of rainwater in underground reservoirs to address capacity deficits in the drainage network) affect the level of risk and runoff in a given area. This could be used to support municipalities in their urban development plans, zoning regulations, urban development concepts, etc.
How?	Hydrodynamic modelling combined with meteorological data, terrain analysis, and risk assessment. Simulation of different scenarios to evaluate the impact of green infrastructure (e.g., green roofs, rain gardens) and technical measures (e.g., underground water storage, enhanced drainage systems).
Limitations	Evaluating the impact of green roofs and storage tanks will not be possible in the course of the project (see limitations in US4.1, US4.2 and US4.3).
Priority	High

Data

Table 4: Potential data sources of interest for the Danube, Zala, RWL.

Model	Dataset	Variables of Interest	Spatial/Temporal Resolution
SaferPlaces	Copernicus CMIP6	Precipitation, total runoff	Global/from 2015 to 2100 for SSP experiments
RIM2D	ECMWF seasonal forecasts	Total precipitation	Global/subdaily (6h) and daily
	EFAS E-Hype Model Precipitation Forecasts	River discharge	Europe/January 2021-present with 7 month lead time, daily or monthly

Climate scenario data (SSP370, SSP585) for 10 models from ISIMIP (Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project, <https://www.isimip.org/>) is available as monthly and daily data and contains the following parameters: humidity, precipitation, short wave radiation, wind speed, air temperature and drought index. The data covers Europe (25°W to 38°E and 34°N to 72°N) with a spatial resolution of 0,5°.

Components used from the Data Fabric

[Figure 16](#) shows the modelling chain for the Danube, Zala, RWL. This modelling chain utilizes the Danube and SaferPlaces models in order to model flooding at a city scale, precipitation projections in the West Balaton Region, an impact assessment, and/or a multi-criteria analysis from the CLIMADA model. Precipitation projections from ECMWF and the EFAS E-Hype model are potential data sources which could be utilized for the SaferPlaces model for future flood forecasts at a city scale. These outputs will then feed into the CLIMADA model. The exposure layer will again come from OSM. The Danube Model outputs of flood return periods will also be utilized as input into the hazard layer of the CLIMADA model, to show future flood scenarios. The final impact assessment produced by the CLIMADA model will show economic and climate change impacts in the West Balaton Region, and be made available via a web GUI. A tentative development would also be the implementation of a multi-criteria assessment, which would enable the evaluation of adaptation measures with climate change in the Zala Region. However, this development is still under discussion with stakeholders in this RWL.

Figure 16: modelling chain for the Danube, Zala, RWL.

3.4 RWL 4 - Rhine-Erft Region, Germany

The Rhine-Erft Region RWL seeks to communicate climate adaptation measures to citizens and stakeholders under the Rhine-Erft Region jurisdiction, in order to support the Erftverband's efforts to strengthen the water management expertise for the region. The Data Fabric in the context of this RWL is therefore to create a centralized platform where citizens and stakeholders in the region can look to for climate change information, as well as data pertaining to disaster events from the past, and in the possible near-future. The following personas and user stories were created in-tandem with the Rhine-Erft RWL to meet these requirements, and provide information that will be useful to employees at the Erftverband, as well as citizens within this region.

Personas

Title	Erftverband
Name	Emil
Organization	Erftverband
Responsibility (in general)	Provide information about water levels, discharge and the hydrological situation in the catchment area of the Erft in general, to responsible organizations on request, and through the Erftverband platform HÖWIS (flood information and warning system Erft)

Title	Municipalities
Name	Margot
Organization	Employee on municipal level with tasks in the field of disaster (risk) management (e.g. major, regulatory office, fire department)
Responsibility (in general)	e.g. assess (hydrological) situations to warn and inform citizens, manage disasters on municipal level etc.

Title	Administrative Districts
Name	Arno
Organization	Employee on the level of an administrative district with tasks in the field of disaster (risk) management (e.g. lower water authority, department of disaster control)

Responsibility (in general)	e.g. responsible for Disaster Risk Management; assess (hydrological) situation, inform other administrative levels or organizations such as municipalities, warn and inform citizens, support municipalities during a/an catastrophe/event
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Title	Farmer(s)
Name	Fiona
Organization	Farmer
Responsibility (in general)	Cultivation of crops for the local and over-regional market

User Stories

Title	US4.1 *20% Increase of Green Roof Flood Simulation at the Past, Present, and Future
Who?	Emil, Margot & Arno (Erftverband, municipalities and administrative districts)
What?	A GUI capable of showing/having the user interact with green roofs in the Rhine-Erft Region.
Why?	<p>Having green roofs integrated into output simulations and visualizations would be a great help to see how effective these measures are. This will be a valuable tool to motivate the implementation process.</p> <p>Green roofs are additionally helpful during drought periods, as they not only catch flood waters, but also store water during times of low-precipitation/low water availability in cities and towns.</p>
How?	<p>Output simulations in urban areas/cities and larger villages in the Rhine-Erft Region, including climate change with green roofs, and without green roofs. Ability to input measures in the GUI. Ability to view a cost-benefit analysis of green roof implementation, and an unadapted future/without green roofs.</p> <p>*a 20% increase in green roofs may change based on continued co-production of the GUI with this RWL</p>
Limitations	<p>SaferPlaces uses the SaferRAIN model to simulate pluvial flood mitigation, including the impact of green roofs. The model represents green roofs by modifying surface parameters such as infiltration and storage capacity. However, due to its event-based nature, SaferRAIN captures only the final storage effect, not the dynamic retention and delayed drainage typical of green roofs. Multi-layer interactions, evapotranspiration, and time-dependent outflow are not explicitly simulated. As a result, green roof effects are simplified, focusing on runoff volume reduction rather than full hydrological behavior. This approach provides useful insight for scenario comparison, though with known limitations.</p>
Priority	Low, see limitations

Title	US4.2 1000L Tanks Flood Simulation at the Past, Present, and Future
Who?	Emil, Margot & Arno (Erftverband, municipalities and administrative districts)
What?	A GUI capable of showing/having the user interact with 1000L tanks in the Rhine-Erft Region.
Why?	Similar to the implementation of green roofs, water tanks could also be an extremely useful measure for the city water management and for CCA/DRM with regard to the disaster phase, and ability to store water in times of drought.
How?	Output simulations in urban areas/cities and larger villages in the Rhine-Erft Region, including climate change with 1000L tanks, and without 1000L tanks. Ability to input measures in the GUI. Ability to view a cost-benefit analysis of tank implementation, and an unadapted future/without green roofs.
Limitations	See limitations US4.1
Priority	Low, see limitations

Title	US4.3 1000L Tanks and Green Roofs Flood Simulation(s) with Past Precipitation/Flooding Event Levels
Who?	Emil, Margot & Arno (Erftverband, municipalities and administrative districts)
What?	As the flooding impacts of 2021 were very devastating to the Rhine-Erft Region, having simulations of the event with the adapted measures would help to get a clearer picture of how helpful the measures could be for the future/in a future scenario of a similar, or greater, magnitude.
Why?	To give our stakeholders a sense of the applicability of the proposed adaptation measures
How?	Simulation outputs of the flooding levels seen in 2021 with green roofs and 1000L water tanks. Ability to place measures in the GUI as desired.
Limitations	See limitations US4.1
Priority	Low, see limitations

Title	US4.4 HOWIS User-Friendly Cloud-based Data Storage and Visualization
Who?	Emil (Erftverband), Margot (municipalities) & Arno (administrative districts), general public
What?	A platform that provides the same information as HOWIS does at the moment (water level and discharge at gauges, weather information, links to other important sources of information). Improvement of the visualization of the data of the HOWIS platform to make it easier to understand and more user-friendly.
Why?	The current data present in the HOWIS platform is too complex for non-hydrologists to interpret and understand in a meaningful way; additionally, data in times of disaster events is from a plethora of sources, making it difficult to get a quick overview of the event/hazardous rainfall and weather forecasts (from DWD, the Ministry of Environment, Nature Conservation and Transport of the State of North Rhine-Westphalia, the State Agency for Nature, Environment and Consumer Protection of North Rhine-Westphalia, as well as water boards). Thus, an easily accessible and centralised cloud-based storage to analyse and visualise data would be beneficial to support flood-risk management.
How?	<p>Creation of a connected systems API with improved data visualization and management. Integration of this data into the cloud-based Data Fabric infrastructure.</p> <p>Information to be visualized:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Water level and discharge at gauges: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Source: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ API/Service: CSA ■ Dataprovider: Erftverband ○ Visualization: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Marker on map coloured based on attribute (e.g. water level, precipitation,...) ■ Time series client with means to compare various time series of different stations and attributes ● Weather information: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ DWD Warnings ○ Rain Radar (raster timeseries) ○ Source: DWD webservice ● Links to other important sources of information: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Weatherforecast ○ Hydrological situation report for NRW ○ Hydrological situation in RLP ○ etc.
Limitations	The idea of developing a platform to replace HOWIS arose during discussions in the DIRECTED consortium, as there was a lack of technical need and support from the RWL 4 stakeholders in the beginning of the project. In parallel with the progress on the user stories, independently of the DIRECTED project, the Erftverband decided to rework its HOWIS platform. A restructuring and revision of several parts of the digital environment at the Erftverband is now planned. It was therefore mutually agreed that the revision of the HOWIS platform would no longer be tackled as part of the DIRECTED project, but that the focus would instead be on the other user stories.
Priority	Low, see limitations.

Title	US4.5 Simulation Sandbox
Who?	Emil (Erftverband employee), (Arno (employee of administrative district))
What?	A platform covering the catchment area of the Erft which allows testing the impact of different measures in flood protection and Climate Change Adaptation (e.g. flood retention basins, green roofs, tanks, unsealing).
Why?	Hydrodynamic modelling is a time-intensive process. To enhance the efficiency of testing various measures, it would be advantageous to have the capability to test them more rapidly and in conjunction with other measures. As of now, we lack the opportunity to quickly simulate and test planned measures, especially for measures which have a spatially large impact.
How?	A hydrodynamic model for the Erft catchment will be set up using both RIM2D and the SaferPlaces suite, enabling users to visualize simulated flooded areas and water depths across the catchment under various precipitation or river discharge scenarios (e.g., different return periods) and mitigation measures (e.g., surface unsealing, green roofs, etc.). Changes to the model's boundary conditions and settings will be implemented on the DataFabric platform either by modifying the RIM2D input files (such as precipitation files and infiltration rasters) or through the SaferPlaces API. Subsequently, simulations with the updated setup will be run, and the results will be presented in a user-friendly format.
Limitations	The current feature set of SaferPlaces would have the capability to model physical barriers, water tanks and potentially flood retention basins (more specification of the nature of retention needed). The flood mitigation measures can be simulated via API, however the Data Fabric front end needs to develop specific design editing tools (polyline, points). In regard to RIM2D, some elements such as underpasses and bridges cannot be represented in the domain. Moreover, to allow users to modify certain model parameters (such as the simulation domain boundary), the Data Fabric front end must implement specialized design editing tools (e.g., polylines, points) and support modifications to RIM2D model files on the backend. Further on, Since RIM2D does not account for certain hydrological processes (e.g., groundwater, vegetation), pluvial simulations cannot be conducted for the entire Erft catchment due to potential inaccuracies but instead fluvial flood simulations will be implemented which require river discharge data.
Priority	High

Title	US4.6 Agricultural Modelling
Who?	Margot (municipalities), Arno (administrative districts) & Fiona (farmer)
What?	An opportunity to see the impacts of climate extremes (flood, drought) on agricultural areas in the region under different climate change scenarios. Information about the assumed yield on a specific agricultural area in dependency of different crops and climate change scenarios in the region.
Why?	In order to assess the impacts of climate change on agriculture there is currently no tool available. The results of such a tool could be very useful for agricultural adaptation (other crops, irrigation, etc.) and the planning of CCA measures.
How?	Simulation of floods in agricultural areas could be undertaken with the SaferPlaces or RIM2D models. This would be achieved through the hydrodynamic models set-up for the Erft catchment, which will then provide water depths and other flow properties for further analysis. The Cost benefit analysis with considering the effects of climate change could be done with the CLIMADA model. The results of the ABSOLUT Model (PIK) for modelling of crop yields under different climate change scenarios will be visualised. This includes the comparison of the yields of different crops in the RWL region under different climate change scenarios. Time series and maps of the projected yields will be displayed.
Limitations	<p>ABSOLUT's spatial resolution depends on the data availability as past weather and yield observations are needed to calibrate the model. These are hardly available below district level. For European scale modelling NUTS-2 regions are used.</p> <p>In RIM2D, certain elements like underpasses and bridges cannot be represented within the hydrodynamic model. Additionally, to enable users to modify specific model parameters (such as the simulation domain boundary), the Data Fabric front end must incorporate specialized design editing tools (e.g., polylines, points) and support modifications to RIM2D model files on the backend. Moreover, as RIM2D does not consider certain hydrological processes (e.g., groundwater, vegetation), pluvial simulations cannot be performed for the entire Erft catchment due to potential inaccuracies. Instead, fluvial flood simulations will be implemented, requiring river discharge data.</p> <p>SaferPlaces can be used to simulate pluvial and fluvial flood event in agricultural areas with some limitation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Simplified Green-Ampt infiltration model ● Fluvial flood possible only for overtopping and banks breaching with 2D hydrodynamic or simplified filling and spilling model. ● Hydrological calculation for the entire basin is not available , the flood event must be characterised by pluvial intensity or through specific volume of water discharge along the river. ● Spatial Resolution limited to DTM resolution
Priority	Medium

Title	US4.7 Dam Break Scenarios
Who?	Margot & Arno (Municipalities and administrative districts)
What?	Scenarios that show/visualize the impacts that certain dam breaks (e.g. dam of a flood retention basins) would have during an event.
Why?	During the flood event of July 2021, people in DRM on municipal and district level were afraid of the break of dams in the region. On the one hand because this for sure would have had severe consequences and on the other hand because nobody could estimate the impact and extent of such a dam break. In order to be prepared and make decisions during an event, knowledge about the potential hazards is important.
How?	<p>Dam break simulations can be achieved with the RIM2D model. Cost benefit analysis of different measures such as dam reinforcement could be done with the CLIMADA model. Options for DEM provision:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Prepare scenario DEMs beforehand and the user selects them from a list. b. Have a tool ready to adjust the DEM on the fly before passing it to RIM2D. c. Let the user upload a scenario DEM.
Limitations	As RIM2D solves the local-inertia approximation of the Shallow Water Equations, it might not be able to achieve the most accurate results in simulating dam-breaks. Some data on the level of breach or stored water levels are required for the simulations which may or may not be available. RIM2D requires an updated DEM for each dam break scenario.
Priority	High

Title	US4.8 Pluvial Early Warning and Nowcasting for DRR
Who?	Margot (municipalities), Arno (administrative districts)
What?	To support PLUVIAL FLOOD risk management, a web-based and very easy-to-use tool is needed for the Erft catchment area, with which the effects of a flood event can be modeled very quickly. With the help of this application, the effect of smaller flood protection measures, such as barriers made of sandbags, can be visualized.
Why?	In an emergency, such an application can help to assess the impact of a flood event and support decisions such as the evacuation of certain locations and the implementation of acute flood protection measures.
How?	Exploiting RADAR data and weather forecast will be possible to generate high resolution pluvial flood map in urban areas The Data Fabric will be able to automatically ingest (via API) Rainfall intensity data from RADAR and Weather forecast , the Saferplaces will execute pluvial flood hazard simulation to support early warning and forecast.
Limitations	
Priority	Medium

Data

The following table gives an overview of models used and data set required in RWL 4.

Table 5: Models and data sources of interest for the Rhine-Erft Region, RWL.

Model	Dataset	Variables of Interest	Spatial/Temporal Resolution
SaferPlaces	Copernicus CMIP6	Precipitation, total runoff	global/from 2015 to 2100 for SSP experiments
RIM2D	LANUV gauging station data (many datasets)	precipitation	Rhine-Erft Region/every 3 mins
	DWD Warnings (used by HOWIS)	precipitation	Germany, Rhine-Erft Region/last 3 hours from current time
	EFAS E-Hype Model Precipitation Forecasts	River discharge	europe/january 2021-present with 7 month lead time, daily or monthly

Components used from the Data Fabric

Figure 17 shows the modelling chain for the Rhine-Erft RWL. This modelling chain utilizes the SaferPlaces, RIM2D, and CLIMADA models. Input data for the SaferPlaces model could include historical precipitation in the case of “stress testing” past scenarios with adaptation measures, as well as forecast precipitation and gauging station data to be fed into RIM2D to simulate adaptation measures under future climate scenarios, such as SSPs. Per discussions with WP 2, there are two different approaches to modelling the adaptation measures for the Rhine-Erft RWL, however for the purposes of this document, the most feasible modelling chain has been displayed using SaferPlaces for both water tanks and green roof simulations. As SaferPlaces contains a parameter for simulating water tanks and infiltration capacity, this parameter will be used for the simulation of adaptation measures by water capacity of green roofs and water tanks. This layer then feeds into the CLIMADA model for a cost-benefit analysis, with hazard coming from the population distribution, and the impact function being calibrated based on outputs from RIM2D. Finally, these layers will be displayed in an output GUI. Parts of this modelling chain, particularly with SaferPlaces, may also be made interactive depending on stakeholder requests. Details of interactive capabilities with the Data Fabric for this RWL are described in D5.4.

Figure 17: modelling chain for the Rhine-Erft Region RWL.

4 Conclusion

This deliverable details the low-level architecture of the DIRECTED Data Fabric. The architecture is designed in a modular and federated way. Technical components have been described and necessary interfaces have been identified. The driving requirements stem from the discussions with the RWL hosts and their stakeholders as summarised in personas and user stories in [Section 3](#). The components constituting the core Data Fabric are selected from proven Open Source Solutions as well for the authorization and access control as well as for the Spatial Data Infrastructure managing the data in the Data Fabric. Models will be interoperably integrated where possible. For some closed source solutions, only the pre-defined model results and outputs can be integrated. Complexity of data discovery and data access and orchestration of processes is hidden from the user and encapsulated in web-based front-end components. Additionally, the Data Fabric offers APIs to retrieve data and results through existing Web and desktop GIS applications.

Based on the defined architecture, the implementation of the modular components of the Data Fabric can now be carried out. In order to ensure that the developments will continue to address the needs and requirements of the users in the RWL, iterative reviews of the solution with RWL hosts and stakeholders will be established. This co-development phase is i.e. important for the design and development of the customised information products, which for some RWL will be a dedicated web application and for others a layer that is imported into existing solutions. Hence, the Data Fabric will showcase how improved interoperability contributes to DRM and CCA.

4.1 Constraints

The Data Fabric is designed to support open standards and to be as flexible as possible. However, only a selection of different data sets and models are exemplarily integrated in the prototype of the Data Fabric. This does not guarantee full flexibility to integrate virtually every model or data set. Description of the processes (i.e., wrapped models) and metadata of processes, models and data are provided guiding the user in integrating new data and setting up new model chain runs.

The Data Fabric is a tool provided to assess risks and impacts of natural hazards based on the integrated models. The responsible use of the Data Fabric is supported with guides and questionnaires (see also Deliverable D5.3 and D5.4). However, this cannot be enforced by the Data Fabric as such, but the Data Fabric will document model runs in order to provide means to scrutinise and audit results generated by the Data Fabric.

The Data Fabric developed within DIRECTED is a highly modular system of mainly open source components. Along with the software, there will be scripts to deploy the Data Fabric

in cloud environments. The operation of the Data Fabric beyond DIRECTED can in general also be achieved in subsets.

4.2 Licences

The main components of the Data Fabric rely on open source solutions and as such will the Data Fabric also adhere to the individual licences of used libraries and solutions. Some models are however not published under an open source licence and only model results can be used in the Data Fabric - not the model on request.

Besides the software, data also has a licence for usage. Information will be requested during the integration of data sets from the Data Steward entering new data. For model runs based on input data, a suitable licence will be suggested and needs to be confirmed by the creator of the model chain generating those results.

Licensing will not change after the DIRECTED project, but access granted within DIRECTED to dedicated software solutions of partners might be retained and individual agreements between RWL and software providers need to be made.

Annex 1: Acceptance Test Report

Checklist Table

Item	Means of verification
Public money - public code	The Code is freely available on GitHub (or other open platforms) and can be re-used under an open source licence.
Interoperable interfaces	Interfaces follow open standards (e.g. OGC, W3C).
FAIR data	The available resources are <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Findable through the Data Fabric • Accessible, where needed, limited to authorized users • Interoperable following open standards (e.g. OGC, W3C) • Re-usable under a given licence with documented meta-data on the data's origin, the generating process and ethical aspects
Authentication and Authorization	User management exists and follows accepted standards. Access-restricted resources can only be accessed by authorized users. Users can login to the Data Fabric and access their approved resources.
Language support	Tools and services are designed to be localizable by using i18n patterns + l10n in frontend (and backend).
(Composable) Processes via API	Models can be executed via API. Model outputs can be collected in interoperable formats allowing to build workflows.
Data steward	Data steward role requirements implemented allowing data upload, metadata creation and documented impact assessment for selected use cases.
Data visualizations	Common data types and formats can be visualized (/processed) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • maps • time series • static data • non-spatial data
User portal	A user portal/environment which may provide different UI components in a coherent way (not strict for all components).

Documentation	Documentation of implemented common administrative tasks and workflows.
Operations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Change management (via version control) ● Automatic deployment pipelines ● Consistent configuration within deployment ● Re-using/re-applying recipes on different deployments ● Vulnerability scanning of images and running containers ● Monitoring and alerting pipelines <p>Follow Infrastructure as Code (IaC), DevOps and GitOps principles.</p>
Scalable Infrastructure	Running processes and service components can be scaled horizontally (see 12 factor app).
Ethical aspects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Conformance to GDPR ● Raised awareness while using the Data Fabric through dedicated information icons and detailed explanations

Partners

